

D7.1 Definition of Test Procedures as a Protocol

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Deliverable Information sheet

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Executive summary

This deliverable includes:

- A summary of the planned MARBEL test procedures at all assembly levels: cell, module and pack.
- Each test procedure is documented with respective test setup (if applicable) and the test profiles to be applied.
- Where applicable, respective standards are consulted and linked to the test procedure description.

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List of abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BMS	Battery Management System
BOL	Begin of Life
BP	Battery Pack
CAN	Controller Area Network
CC	Constant Current
CC/CV	Constant Current / Constant Voltage
DC	Direct Current
DUT	Device Under Test
ECM	Equivalent Circuit Model
eVIL	Electric Vehicle in the Loop
HPPC	Hybrid Pulse Power Characterization
HV	High Voltage
iSCM	Integrated Smart Cell Manager
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NMC	Nickel Manganese Cobalt
OCV	Open Circuit Voltage
PCB	Printed Circuit Board
RC	Resistance/Capacitance
RESS	Rechargeable Energy Storage System
RL	Reinforcement Learning
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
SOC	State of Charge
TR	Thermal Runaway
WLTC	Worldwide Harmonized Light Vehicle Test Procedure / Cycle

Introduction

The MARBEL project develops a high-performant and modular battery pack, which is subject to a comprehensive testing campaign throughout the project. Since the full final pack is made up from several sophisticated subsystems, the development phases are accompanied by the testing activities to provide data and insights into the designs at all stages of the development. This is mainly to allow for iteration loops and an ongoing improvement of the designs, but also to generate data from very early stages of the available devices-under-test (DUT), even if those are still conceptual. Therefore, the MARBEL testing approach considers all development stages, accounting for a high need of test data especially when the DUT's maturity is still low.

Figure 1: Discrepancy between maturity of DUT and need for measurement data.

In MARBEL, test setups are created that are either made up of the DUTs themselves (e.g. cells) or use the available DUTs to create interim or pre-mature test setups to anticipate the behavior of upcoming, more mature DUT levels such as modules. In addition, this bridging of DUTs and building sophisticated test setups allows for evaluating the applicability of test procedures and thus a refining of the testing strategy, even before the targeted DUT level is available in the project.

This deliverable therefore describes and explains the intended test procedures to be applied at the different DUT levels. Single cells are subject to comprehensive experiments, whereas they are used to build a conceptual cooling setup to iterate through potential improvements of an early-stage cooling concept. Once modules are available, they are considered for testing as well as used to build a “pre-pack” setup, by connecting them and attaching additional cooling components to mimic the final full pack system. Finally, the full MARBEL battery pack is used to demonstrate its behavior under real world conditions.

Figure 2: MARBEL testing approach: use any available DUT level to create sophisticated setups and test data.

In the following, a quick introduction into the DUT levels of MARBEL is given. They are used in the described test setups and -procedures, whereas a separation is made between performance-related tests and safety-related tests.

1. Assembly levels of DUTs to be tested within the scope of MARBEL

The MARBEL battery pack (BP) consists of several sub-components. The single cells form the smallest unit of DUTs. To build a module, 12 cells are connected and equipped with additional components for thermal conditioning. The modules carry different units and printed circuit boards (PCB), named “integrated smart cell manager” (iSCM) and slave boards to monitor and communicate the main parameters to the rest of the battery system. A total number of 16 or 32 modules are connected to create the 400 V version or the 800 V switchable version of the MARBEL battery, respectively. The interconnection of the module-based battery management system (BMS) components with up to two SuperMaster boards complete the full BMS, which constantly monitors the whole system to avoid any operation outside a safe operating area.

During the experiments conducted with the MARBEL DUTs, the following main parameters/information are monitored and recorded:

- Testbench values including (cell) voltage, current, temperatures, charged/discharged Ah, power, charged/discharged energy
- BMS-measured values including (cell) voltage, (cell) temperatures, status information such as balancing, errors/warnings
- Additional test-devices, e.g. cooling conditioning unit delivering coolant temperature and flowrate
- Images, videos

Given the previously described testing strategy of MARBEL, the different DUT-levels will all be subject to thorough test campaigns to validate them as soon as they are available. The different DUTs are briefly introduced in the following.

1.1. Li-Ion cells

The cells assembled in the MARBEL battery pack are high-energy prismatic cells.

Figure 3: Prismatic Li-Ion-cells used in the MARBEL Battery Pack.

The following table gives a short overview of the main cell characteristics, which are linked to important monitoring processes during the performed test procedures. Many of the mentioned

parameters are directly linked to the safety behavior of the DUT, thus the conducted tests must not be continued if any safety limit is exceeded.

Table 1: Relevant parameters of the MARBEL BP cells.

Item	Value	Description
Cell chemistry	Graphite / NMC	The cells consist of a graphite anode and an NMC cathode.
Cell capacity	C_{cell}	This is the rated capacity of the cells. It is related to a 1C discharge. Since the value is not yet fixed, it is further referred to as C_{cell} .
Cell nominal voltage	U_{nom}	This is the nominal voltage of the cells. It is used for calculations such as power capability of the later battery system and for benchmarking. It is further referred to as U_{nom} .
Cell voltage limits (degradation)	$U_{max_degrade}$, $U_{min_degrade}$	These upper and lower voltage limits define the limits during operational use, meaning the cells shall not be operated outside of this voltage window to avoid accelerated aging. The values are further referred to as $U_{max_degrade}$ and $U_{min_degrade}$.
Cell voltage limits (safety)	U_{max_safety} , U_{min_safety}	These upper and lower voltage limits define the safety limits the cell must not exceed to avoid hazardous situations. The values are further referred to as U_{max_safety} and U_{min_safety} .
Cell temperature limits (degradation)	T_{max_degrad} , T_{min_degrad}	These upper and lower temperature limits are related to the degradation of the cells. To avoid accelerated aging, the cells should not be operated outside of this temperature window. The values are further referred to as T_{max_degrad} and T_{min_degrad} .
Cell temperature limits (safety)	T_{max_safety} , T_{min_safety}	These are the upper and lower temperature limits of the cells related to safety. To avoid hazardous events like thermal runaway or leaking, the cells must not be operated outside of this temperature window. The values are further referred to as T_{max_safety} and T_{min_safety} .
Cell current limit (degradation)	I_{max_degrad}	This limit specifies the maximum current allowed to avoid accelerated aging. It is defined in the cell datasheet and will further be referred to as I_{max_degrad} .
Cell current limit (safety)	I_{max_safety}	This limit specifies the maximum current allowed for safety reasons. Going above this limit must be prevented by the monitoring system of the MARBEL BP. This value is defined in the cell datasheet and will further be referred to as I_{max_safety} .

1.2. MARBEL modules

The MARBEL modules are very maneuverable and modular design-based units. Each module consists of 12 cells, which are arranged in a 6s2p configuration. Given the maximum voltage of approximately 4.25 V per cell (typical for NMC), the maximum module voltage is at around 25.5 V. In between the cells that form the modules, several cooling-system-related components are placed, which mainly contribute to the overall safety of the modules as well as conduct the heat from the cells towards the top- and bottom-cooling plates, which themselves are integral parts of the pack's housing.

Figure 4: View of the final MARBEL modules.

The modules will provide the option to electrically connect a testbench or further modules to apply certain power profiles in addition to a CAN-based communication interface to receive and record values measured by the module's BMS (iSCMs and slave-board). Since the MARBEL modules can operate in a fully standalone manner (linked to 2nd-Life requirements), the data communicated by the BMS is comprehensive enough to monitor and keep them within a safe operating area during the experiments, in addition to the values measured by the executing test system. Equipped with cooling-related components such as thermal fins, thermal pads and compression pads, the module can easily be attached to cooling plates to allow for the simulation and validation of a thermal conditioning scenario.

For a comprehensive description of the MARBEL module design as well as the BMS architecture they are equipped with, reference shall be given to deliverables D5.2 and D4.4, respectively.

1.3. MARBEL battery pack

The MARBEL battery pack combines the modules in a modular and scalable way together with a flexible junction box to allow for a safe operation and a proper interconnection to the specific application. Within the MARBEL project, two versions of the full battery pack are assembled, a 400 V and an 800 V version. Inside the 400 V pack, 16 modules (6s2p each) are connected in series, which sums up to a total number of cells of 192 in a 96s2p configuration. Thus, given the maximum module voltage of 25.5 V as mentioned above, this results in a maximum pack voltage of around 408 V. In the 800 V case, 32 modules are interconnected, whereas the junction box allows for a switching between the 400 V/800 V level. To do so, it changes the connection to either 16 and 16 modules in series, which results in a configuration of 192s2p giving a maximum voltage of 816 V, or a parallel connection of 16 and 16 modules resulting in 96s4p, same voltage level as in the 400 V pack, but doubling the nominal capacity of the system. This switching option enables the pack to adapt to different scenarios and applications, such as driving at 400 V with a higher capacity and charging at 800 V when available. Both packs have the cooling channels as integral parts of their housing structure.

Figure 5: MARBEL 800 V pack with transparent cover to get a look inside.

As can be seen in the 800 V pack picture, the junction box is connected to the main HV-interfaces with two lines, one for the 800 V charger connection (e.g. in a vehicle scenario, eVIL testbench) and one for the drivetrain connection (“regular”, 400 V mode).

In the 400 V pack version, the power electronics take less space, since no switching function is needed and thus the regular HV contactors are fitted inside the DC-box housing in addition to a DC-Filter.

Figure 6: MARBEL 400 V pack with removed top cover plate to get a look inside.

For more detailed information about the pack design, the deliverables D5.6 and D5.7 shall be mentioned.

2. Test procedures related to performance demonstration.

Investigating the performance of the developed battery system within the MARBEL project is an important and inevitable step to validate that the targeted KPIs and requirements have been met. By defining different test procedures, the behavior of the system and its main parameters, such as capacity, internal resistance, power capability and other performance indicators, are deduced.

Additionally, the thermal behavior under demanding driving cycles / test profiles and the performance of the developed thermal system must be validated, to ensure a safe operation under different environmental conditions, a maximum life-expectancy of the system as well as aligning the real test results with the developed models, including AI-based models to detect early failures.

Besides many standards and regulations describing sets of test procedures, a prominent one is the ISO12405 [1]. It defines different tests related to the performance of a battery system, whereas certain tests described in the following are oriented towards this regulation, however, specifically designed for revealing parameters of the MARBEL system focusing on e.g. model validation and validating KPIs that were set in the beginning of the project. Additionally, the developed AI methods in the project (see deliverable D4.1) require a high amount of cyclic data, which is why additionally continuous cycling tests at cell and “quasi-module-level” (see section 2.2.1.) are conducted to generate the necessary data. Regarding continuous cycling, not only standard cycles are used, but also realistic driving cycles (WLTC) to validate the cell’s degradation behavior combined with their thermal performance.

Thus, the performance validation of the developed MARBEL system will consist of tests beginning at cell level, quasi-module-level combined with a prototypic cooling setup, module level with fully equipped BMS communication capabilities as well as full system level. For the latter, the 800 V system was chosen to be validated in terms of performance, which is for several reasons. First of all, this pack with a switchable configuration is the one intended to be used in a vehicle application: it can be switched between 400 V (driving mode) and 800 V (charging mode) through a junction box, which also incorporates the main contactors to switch off the main output of the battery. Therefore, the 800 V-capable system will be integrated into the eVIL-testbench (see deliverable D6.4), which represents the “full-vehicle-application”, including changing use-phases of charging and driving. Therefore, a realistic driving cycle scenario as given by the WLTC cycle will be chosen to validate the behavior. Additionally, another 800 V prototype will be used for general performance tests, including power capability in different operating conditions, switching behavior of the junction box, BMS communication and interoperability with external systems (testbench, additional sensors) as well as cybersecurity aspects covering planned attacks on the BMS and its communication channels. It is also planned to complement the environmental conditions set at the eVIL testbench with additional ones, to allow for a more comprehensive validation of the cycle-life performance.

As a general introductory overview, the performance tests that are planned will include the following:

- cell level:
 - general characterization tests to measure main parameters:
 - quasi-OCV measurement
 - capacity validation at different C-rates
 - internal resistance measurement by HPPC profile
 - continuous cycling tests at different temperatures and C-rates to extend and complement information given in the cell datasheet and provide the data for developed AI-methods
- module level:
 - “quasi-module-level”: a test setup consisting of two cells connected in parallel (1s2p) to mimic a part-configuration of the final modules (which are 6s2p). This setup is extended with a prototypic cooling system, to allow for an early concept validation before real modules are available and to advance cycle-life experiments additionally to measuring pressure force evolution over the cycles.
 - module level in their final design: those tests will cover general standard characterizations of the modules including their BMS communications as well as functionalities like cell balancing. In addition, multiple modules will be connected in a 3s configuration to a) validate the interconnection of BMS communication and b) advance the testing progress with a “quasi-pack-configuration” before the

full packs are available. Another addition to this setup will be the integration of the final cooling system configuration to one module (including top- and bottom cooling plates), to allow for a validation of the real thermal performance and have a direct comparison to the uncooled modules.

- 2nd-Life tests: those tests will include specific load profiles related to 2nd-Life applications and validate the suitability and performance in such scenarios.
- pack level:
 - single 800 V pack: this pack is planned to be used to validate main characteristics under different conditions (temperature, current demand, cooling conditions) as well as cybersecurity aspects.
 - eVIL testbench: an 800 V configurable pack will be integrated into the eVIL testbench, consisting of an eMotor-testbench and a battery testbench that are combined to evaluate a real drivetrain scenario and investigate the performance under realistic driving conditions. These conditions will also include fast charging phases, which require a switching of the configuration to 800 V and thus include a validation of the switching procedure done in the pack's power electronics (junction box).

2.1. Cell level

As described in D3.1 with the previous cell types, a comprehensive set of test procedures is required to deduce the main characteristics and parameters of the cells used to be assembled inside the battery pack. Those characterization tests, including OCV-curve measurement as well as HPPC test to deduce the internal resistance, are obligatory to parameterize and tune cell models, more specifically equivalent circuit models (ECM). Therefore, the cells in use are measured at different temperature conditions to get representative data. Additionally, cyclic data is necessary to feed the AI-algorithms and -models and investigate the degradation behavior, which is why additional continuous cycling is performed at different temperature settings.

2.1.1. Initial standard cycle / “formation”

Before the cells are cycled with any test profile, a standard cycle is repeated three times to allow for a deduction of the nominal capacity under nominal conditions. For this experiment, the cell is charged to the max. voltage $U_{max_degrade}$ by a CC/CV charge at a rate of $C/3$, whereas the cutoff current is set to $C/10$. After a rest phase, the cell is discharged to the min. voltage $U_{min_degrade}$ also at a C-rate of $C/3$, which will be taken as reference current to deduce the nominal capacity.

Figure 7: Flowchart "standard cycle" to deduce nominal capacity @ C/3 [A]

It shall be mentioned that not the full cell voltage window is used in this experiment, which is to reserve a slight margin related to the voltage limits according to the datasheet to allow for a better life-expectancy of the cells (e.g. during continuous cycling). This results in a slightly lower nominal capacity than the value mentioned in the cell's datasheet.

2.1.2. Quasi-OCV curve measurement

To measure the OCV-curve of the cells, mainly two approaches can be followed. One approach is to stepwise charge/discharge the cell and let the cell rest for a very long period of time, after which the cell's voltage is measured to deduce the OCV-voltage at the set SOC-point. Since this approach is rather time-consuming, the hereafter depicted method is measuring the OCV by applying a very small test current during charge/discharge and neglecting the load of the cell while measuring the voltage. In this test profile, a measurement current of C/20 is chosen.

Figure 8: Flowchart of "quasi-OCV" measurement @C/20 [A].

2.1.3. Rate capability at different C-rates

This test profile is applied to measure and validate the cell's capacity at different discharge rates. In its flow, the test is comparable to the standard cycle, just a different discharge current is set for each repetition. In this experiment, rates from C/3 [A] to 1C [A] are applied.

Figure 9: Flowchart of "rate capability" test @ C/3 - 1C [A].

2.1.4. HPPC test

An important test is the HPPC (hybrid-pulse-power-characterization), which is used to generate data for a parameterization of e.g. an equivalent circuit model and to validate the power capability of the cell. This test covers the whole SOC-range of the cell (in this case by discharging 10 %-stepwise) and applies current pulses at a certain C-rate to record the voltage response. The

so that the model is calibrated, and its parameters take the optimal value. After the training process, the Neural Network has learned the optimal parameters of the ECM and by applying a new dataset, the predicted SOC is generated through this optimum parameterized ECM.

Figure 11: The training process of the approach for SOC prediction.

2.1.5. Continuous cycling at different operating conditions

In this set of tests, the selected cells will be continuously charged and discharged between the operational cell voltage limits. Thus, one single cycle consists of a full CC/CV charge to $U_{max_degrade}$, followed by an immediate CC-discharge to $U_{min_degrade}$; no rest phase in between. This cycle is repeated until a predefined number is reached. To avoid excessive degradation and to investigate the impact, a reduced voltage window during charge/discharge can be chosen (e.g. margin of 0,1 V to $U_{max/min_degrade}$). The following table shows the intended number of cells and conditions.

Table 2: Conditions applied during the continuous cycling / cycle aging tests.

10 °C	25 °C	35 °C
1 cell @ C/3 [A] charge and C/2 [A] discharge continuously	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 cell @ C/3 [A] charge and C/2 [A] discharge continuously 1 cell @ C/3 [A] charge and 1C [A] discharge continuously 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 cell @ C/3 [A] charge and C/2 [A] discharge continuously 1 cell @ C/3 [A] charge and 1C [A] discharge continuously

The intention of the continuous cycling test is on one hand to investigate the degradation behavior of the cells in terms of capacity fade as well as internal resistance increase. Even though limited information is available from the cell manufacturer, self-recorded measurement data is vital to have reasonable information and a proof of cell behavior under different operating conditions. In addition, the data available from the manufacturer does only show a trend-curve for the

degradation behavior for certain conditions, however, no measurement data that mirrors the continuous cycling of the cell is given. Thus, and on the other hand, the generated data from these tests will be used to train AI-based reinforcement learning models, which will be used to generate an alternative version of equivalent circuit models of the cells compared to their “classical” versions. The latter will be parameterized with data originating from interim checkup tests and more specifically from HPPC as described previously, which will be applied during these checkups to monitor the main parameters of the cells along their cycle life. Therefore, this continuous cycling test will be a repeating sequence of charge/discharge cycles until a certain number of cycles is reached, then followed by a checkup test sequence and finally starting over with the cycling again. The exact number of cycles, after which the checkup tests will be conducted is to be defined according to the limitations of data acquisition of the test benches in use as well as based on the conditions and overall testing time available. A value between 300 – 500 cycles is reasonable. The exact number will be named and reported in the test result evaluation in D7.2.

2.2. Module level

The fully assembled modules are the first DUTs that provide a full functionality including data communications as well as enhanced calculations and control of the values during the applied experiments. It is therefore of highest interest to investigate the behavior of single modules in their entirety, including a comparison of the communicated BMS values and the ones originating from the testbench. This data will enable a first modeling of a cell-compound that shows more complexity than the single cells. This is not only due to the mere electrical interconnection of the cells, but also due to the cooling system and its components being integrated into the modules. Thus, the modules can be used to investigate the thermal behavior and the performance of the developed cooling system long before a full battery system is available. Therefore, the tests are started from the earliest stage possible, to accompany other work-packages and allow for design iterations like the cooling system design. The tests to be carried out therefore include:

- early proof of thermal cooling design to allow for iterations by generating feedback data
- full electrical characterization of a single module
- validation of thermal behavior / cooling performance of the module
- interconnection of modules to investigate BMS communication in a scenario with more than one participant
- 2nd-Life tests

2.2.1. Validation of cooling design at an early development stage

2.2.1.1. General setup

At an early stage of the project, it is very probable that no DUT, more specifically no fully assembled module is available that allows for the real measurement-based validation of the cooling concept. However, since the other work-packages have a strong need for data during designing the modules, their housing and their cooling concept, it is necessary to have a proof of concept to allow for iterations and improvements of the system from the very beginning. For that reason, a conceptual test setup is assembled with two cells, to allow for an integration of the cooling system components. A compound of two cells therefore builds a sub-part of a whole module, which is intended to have 12 cells in total, in a configuration of 6s2p. Therefore, two cells connected in parallel, forming a 1s2p configuration, will be a “quasi-module”, that allows the assembly of components like thermal pads, thermal fins and compression pads. In addition, the

cells should allow for an attachment of top and bottom cooling plates, as intended for the full system.

The following graph shows the conceptual design of this test setup.

Figure 12: Conceptual setup view of two cells connected in parallel, sandwiched with cooling design components.

The “sandwich” of cells and components thereby represents the cooling design, whereas the mentioned cooling fins are assembled and structured according to their intended shape as mentioned in the cooling design of D3.5. The different components are stacked and pretensioned according to the cell manufacturer’s specifications, which should support an optimum for the life-expectancy of the cells. The setup therefore allows for the application of a pretension force to the desired value.

In between the different layers of the setup, type K thermoelements measure the temperatures at different spots. It is to be aligned with the thermal design work-package how many sensors and at which position they are placed. The exact placement and the detailed view of the resulting test setup will be described in D7.2 together with the results.

With this test setup, not only the thermal performance of the chosen design can be validated, but also a long-term cycling of the 2p-cell-compound is targeted. For this, an additional measurement of the force-evolution during the cells’ cycle life is foreseen. For this, a force sensor is installed, which continuously monitors the tension force of the “sandwich-compound”. The setup therefore looks like the following illustration:

Figure 13: View of the overall test setup with integrated force measurement and option to pretension the stack.

It can be described as a constrained, pretensioned setup with the option to continuously monitor the force evolution while electrically loading the DUTs (=2p-cell-compound).

2.2.1.2. Testing profile

In terms of electrical load, the test cells are first characterized by the standard test procedures as mentioned above in section 2.1. This will allow for a basic set of parameters at the BOL of the tested cells and a first impression of their thermal characteristics in this setup.

One of the main MARBEL KPIs is linked to charging time, which is why it is of highest importance to validate the intended charging time with this setup, since it is linked to the thermal performance and thus a potential derating of current/power during the charging phase. To meet the intended charging time, a current of 2C is targeted for a recharge from 5 % to 80 % SOC. Based on the cells' datasheet, this current level might be linked to increased heat generation, which is why a thorough monitoring of temperature evolution is vital. To couple the fast-charging phases with the abovementioned cycle-life test, a real driving cycle is applied to the cells which represents driving phases with different demands. Therefore, the WLTC is chosen, which is also mentioned in the topic description of the European Commission Funding and Tenders portal under the LC-BAT-10-2020 proposal call. More specifically, a fast-charge to 80 % is done every 2000 km and two consecutive fast-charges after 6000 km. After this, a new cycle round is started, which always starts with a standard cycle to measure the actual capacity of the cell-compound, whereas the discharge-C-rate can be set according to the desired value (up to 1C). The following flowchart shows the testing profile to be applied:

Figure 14: Flowchart of continuous real-driving cycles with interim fast-charging phases.

For the WLTC profile, the drivetrain parameters of the chosen benchmark vehicle are used. In this case, this corresponds to the Audi e-tron, model 2018/19. Since the WLTC is given by a velocity vs. time format, the e-tron parameters will be used to calculate the current demand back to cell level to apply the respective load onto the 2p-cell-compound test setup. The following graph shows the WLTC:

Figure 15: WLTP in velocity vs. time representation to be used for calculation of cell-level currents.

This test will therefore deliver two main outputs. First, it will deliver data that is linked to the thermal behavior of the 2p-cell-compound during different load scenarios (standard cycles, HPPC, driving cycle according to WLTC, fast charging) to validate the cooling design of the later module. Second, the continuous application of WLTC driving cycles combined with fast charging phases allow for an evaluation of the degradation behavior under these conditions as well as an insight into the pretension force evolution due to its constant monitoring.

2.2.2. Electrical and thermal validation of a full module

As described above, a MARBEL module consists of 12 cells, connected in a 6s2p configuration. Since the modules are fully equipped with iSCMs and BMS slave-boards, they also provide an on-DUT measurement of many different parameters, such as single-cell voltage and -temperature, but also warning and error notifications. Therefore, the module tests deliver the following information:

- General electrical behavior / characteristics of the 6s2p compound and the electrical connections (busbars)
- Measured and communicated values originating from the iSCMs and the slave board
- Functionality of error/warnings created by the BMS
- Thermal performance of the attached cooling system and the final cooling design

Regarding the cooling performance, the tests at the final modules will be linked to the final cooling system design; other than the previously described conceptual cooling design tests. Therefore, it is reasonable to perform comparable driving cycles as done in the conceptual setup, to allow for a comparison of both designs. In addition, a comparison can be made between the uncooled module, more specifically a mere module without top and bottom cooling plate, and a module that is equipped with a full cooling system structure. This reveals limitations of power delivery for the unconditioned case, which is also a highly important information especially when it comes to the ability to fast charge the system.

2.2.2.1. General setup

The general electrical characterization as well as the thermal validation can be integrated into a single setup. Thus, a fully functional module is equipped with top and bottom cooling plates according to the battery pack's cooling design, which allows for a thermal control unit to be integrated into the test environment. Since the cooling plates are integral parts of the final pack design, special parts must be produced for this test setup to integrate the module into a top and bottom cooling. The intended setup is shown in the following graph.

Figure 16: Module test setup with integrated top- and bottom cooling plates for a full characterization of electrical and thermal behaviour.

As shown in the picture, the module is placed on a bottom cooling profile, which allows a thermal connection of the module's bottom cooling fins and the plate itself via thermal pads. Those pads will be assembled already when the module leaves the assembly line, since this experimental assembly situation on the bottom plates is the same as during the full pack assembly. Regarding the top cooling, the only difference to the pack-situation will be the length needed for this setup. The shown top cooling rails only cover the module's top lid, which itself thermally connects the cells' terminals with the top cooling rail. It is therefore intended to use a U-shaped top cooling rail that will conduct the coolant. Both plates, top and bottom, are supplied with coolant via a y-connector to have a parallel coolant flow, just as present in the final pack cooling design.

During the measurements, the thermal situation is investigated with several type K thermoelement sensors, which are installed at different positions. Potential positions are shown in the following graph, whereas the exact position and number of sensors will be reported in D7.2.

Figure 17: Positioning of thermal sensors in the test setup

2.2.2.2. Testing profile

Since this test setup is additionally equipped with thermal system components, it allows for the application of high demanding current/power profiles. Thus, besides the standard characterization tests mentioned at cell level, the WLTC continuous cycling and fast charging is performed. The respective values and limitations are adapted according to the module's main parameters (max. voltage, C-rate etc.).

The delivered innovative thermal management system control strategy as described in D3.6 is also integrated into this testing setup. With this integration, the coolant pump used during the experiments can directly be controlled with the outputs of this strategy, which enables its live validation in addition to the thermal performance of the module. Given the structure of the control strategy as reported in D3.6, different input values are required:

- T_Bat_degC: the “battery” temperature, which in this scenario is calculated to the average value of all six temperature values measured by the iSCM boards

$$T_{Bat_{degC}} = \frac{\sum T_{iSCMs}}{6}$$
- SOC: the module's state of charge, which is not calculated by the module's slave board and thus must be received by the testbench
- T_NT_degC: the ambient temperature, which depending on the setup placement is set/measured accordingly
- T_cf_degC: the actual coolant temperature, which is measured and received from the coolant pump
- T_cell_bus_degC: the cells' temperatures as a vector input, which is used by the control strategy to calculate the temperature spread inside the module. This vector is built from the received cell temperatures measured by the BMS/iSCMs
- Operation_mode: this value is constantly set to 1, which corresponds to operation mode “driving”
- Vehicle_Off: fixed to 0
- Vehicle_Thermal_Ready: fixed to 1

- Passive_Enabled: fixed to 0
- Active_Cooling_Enabled: fixed to 1
- Active_Heating_Enable: fixed to 1
- Power_Available: fixed to 1

Figure 18: Innovative control strategy to control the coolant pump during the experiments based on live measurement data.

The control strategy then outputs the targeted coolant volume flow ($V_{\dot{\text{target}}}$) in l/min, whereas the value corresponds to the cooling system of the full pack, which is why the output value must be divided by 8 (because of 8 separate cooling “rows” in the pack). In addition, the targeted setpoint of coolant temperature is given ($T_{\text{target_cf_degC}}$) together with a power output for a potential PTC heater ($P_{\text{PTC_Heater_W}}$), which however is not used in this test scenario, since the cooling pump is able to fully condition the fluid (heating and cooling) and therefore is already accounted for in the target setpoint temperature. The $LVL1_State$ and $LVL2_State$ are output information about the internal state machine.

Finally, at least the following test profiles are executed:

- Standard cycles, HPPC test, capacity validation, OCV-curve
- Driving cycle according to WLTC
- Fast charging with targeted current of 2C

The respective test parameters (limit values, set current rates etc.) are adapted according to the module parameters.

2.2.3. Interconnection of modules to build “pack-like” structure

Given the fact that the full battery pack systems are the last DUT assembly level to be available in the project, it is reasonable to perform experiments on the interconnection of several modules to build a test setup that represents at least a part of a full battery pack. Just like the previously described conceptual test setup for the cooling design which builds a module-like structure, this setup described in the following allows for the validation of multiple factors:

- General interoperability and behavior of modules when connected together
- BMS behavior when daisy-chained with other communication participants
- Potential faults and errors originating from the interconnection
- Comparison of thermal performance depending on cooling situation of the connected modules (e.g. one module cooled according to previous section, the others uncooled)

2.2.3.1. General setup

The test setup consists of 3 series-connected modules, which then equals a 18s2p configuration (6s2p per module). In general, this setup is based on the previously described module-setup with integrated cooling and can be extended by adding (uncooled) modules and connecting them accordingly.

Figure 19: Electrical interconnection of modules and BMS daisy-chaining for communication.

2.2.3.2. Testing profile

The applied tests are equal to the ones in the single-module setup, with the only adaptation of overall voltage level and additional BMS values to be monitored. Considering that one of the modules' slave boards must take the role of a master according to the BMS structure, this master-module will also monitor the correct reception and presence of messages from the other modules. Therefore, not only a higher number of measurement values will be available, but also new or different types of potential error/warning messages that can lead to the abortion of the test. If uncooled modules are used while applying demanding test profiles, either the profile or the setup must be adapted (e.g. by removing uncooled modules), to avoid any thermal problems.

2.2.4. 2nd Life tests

To validate the performance of the module after the first life application, tests are done with single modules according to testing profiles originating from applications in a second-life scenario. This is to evaluate also the reusability and compatibility of the modules e.g. with small mobility applications, such as e-bikes or e-scooters. Since a separate deliverable describes these types of tests, reference is given to D7.4 for thorough information. As a quick indication, the 2nd-Life tests include the following:

- Capacity test
- 2nd-Life profiles according to different applications
- Life-expectancy estimations based on cell level test results

2.3. Pack level

As indicated in previous chapters, the full battery pack system is the final instance of DUT to be tested. Therefore, all experimental procedures described for the previous DUT level will be applied at fully pack level, which will allow for a validation of the results achieved previously and to get a full characterization of the performance and its limitations of the full system. Since all modules are equipped with sophisticated measurement circuitry, investigations on e.g. temperature gradients inside the pack can be done which can provide useful input for life expectancy estimations. In addition, the full pack provides the complete BMS architecture including cloud communications, which allows additional tests to be performed related to cyber-security.

2.3.1. Standalone battery pack

The full battery pack comes with all testable components assembled inside its housing. Therefore, it can directly be integrated into a test environment such as a testbench, whereas additional sensors (e.g. thermal sensors) can be placed. All necessary interfaces are provided at the housing of the pack: HV-interfaces, MSDS disconnects, LV-interfaces and coolant inlet/outlet.

2.3.1.1. General setup

For the intended tests, the pack itself is the main setup, which is integrated into the respective testing environment. This can be e.g. a temperature chamber or – in the case of vibration testing – a vibration table the pack is securely fixed to.

Figure 20: Full battery pack to be tested - the full pack is the main part of the test setup.

2.3.1.2. Testing profile

As mentioned, the main characteristics of the pack are measured to deduce its power capability as well as limitations. Thus, the described test profiles are applied:

- Standard cycles, HPPC test, capacity validation, OCV-curve
- max. power limits, max. current limits under different environmental conditions
- Driving cycle according to WLTC
- Fast charging with targeted current of 2C
- Vibration test according to UNECE R100 [3]

Regarding the last point, the vibration test, a short summary of the testing profile shall be given, since it has not been described so far.

For this test, the pack is securely fixed to a vibration testbench by screwing the fixation points located around the housing to the vibration table. The test itself is performed according to the UNECE R100 regulation [3].

All safety measures of the pack (contactor monitoring, BMS, isolation monitoring etc.) are active during the test. Before the vibration test, a standard cycle (according to section 2.1.1.) is performed. During the test, the BMS communication is monitored and the main contactors are closed to simulate a driving scenario. In case of any malfunction/fault, the contactors would open during the test.

1. the pack is fully charged to 100 % SOC, in this scenario by a CC/CV charge at C/3 A to a cutoff current of C/20 A
2. rest phase of 30 minutes
3. vibration test according to profile given in UNECE R100, annex 9A [3]
4. rest phase of at least 1 hour after the end of the test (meanwhile recording and monitoring the BMS data)

After the vibration test, a standard cycle is repeated to demonstrate the full functionality of the pack. If the pack is fully functional and no error messages are highlighted from the BMS that can be linked to the vibration test as root cause, the test can be considered as passed.

Besides the electrical test profiles, the BMS and its communication channels are tested for their cybersecurity performance. Thus, the following experiments are done by utilizing the different interfaces (wired/wireless) of the pack:

- interface security tests to mitigate man-in-the-middle risks
- probing security mechanisms of slave-/master-BMS
- explore potential vulnerabilities in BMS functions, such as unauthorized firmware installation
- sleep deprivation attack: prevent iSCMs from going into a sleep mode to provoke a battery drain
- assess wireless connectivity between iSCMs and BMS-slave boards
 - investigation of security between iSCMs and BMS-slave boards is out of the scope of cloud-communications, since it is linked to inside-battery communications
 - test of Bluetooth low energy communication using man-in-the-middle techniques

2.3.2. Battery pack in eVIL test environment

For the concept and setup description of the eVIL test environment, a separate deliverable D6.4 is available giving detailed information. Therefore, this subsection intends to only give a quick summary of the activities and the main experiments.

The eVIL testbench allows for a real-driving-scenario validation of the MARBEL pack, by combining the battery with a motor-drivetrain testbench to attach a real load to the pack. However, a specialty of the eVIL test environment is that the drivetrain load is not physically connected to the battery, but by a drivetrain simulator. In the same sense, the battery behavior is simulated by a battery simulator that itself is attached to the real motor-drivetrain testbench. This allows for a different location of the battery pack and the real motor testbench.

In the eVIL, the real driving scenario is tested. Therefore, the pack is mainly operated under WLTC driving cycles, whereas changing environmental conditions are simulated by a temperature chamber. In addition, fast charging is performed to complete the real-world scenarios and continue the tests done at conceptual cooling setup and module level as described before.

Figure 21: eVIL testing environment to validate real-world driving scenarios.

3. Test procedures related to safety validation

This chapter gives an overview of the safety-related tests carried out for the MARBEL project at the different DUT levels, just as done for the performance-based tests in the previous sections. The main target is to assess the safety of the cells, modules and the full pack in different “abnormal” test case scenarios. In this way, full pack capabilities to withstand different safety conditions in real-world environments will be assessed. For the definition of the tests, different standards, such as the UN38.3 [4] and UNECE R100 [3] are followed.

3.1. Cell level

The UN38.3 and ECE R100 standards define various testing requirements and -profiles to assess their capability and stability to withstand and overcome the safety protocols during real driving environments. Thus, the following test procedures are performed at cell level to be in line with the regulations:

- thermal abuse test
- overcharge test
- drop test
- impact test
- nail penetration
- crush test

3.1.1. Thermal Abuse Test

The thermal abuse test is essential in the battery industry to evaluate the behavior of the cells and their thermal stability at extremely high temperatures, which helps to assess safety risks like thermal runaway scenarios. The test case scenario for the MARBEL cell is that the SOC of the cell is set to 50 %, and the test is initialized to reach a temperature of 100 °C. Once the temperature reaches 100 °C, then test is continued until the thermal runaway is triggered. When the thermal runaway is started, a rest phase is done until the thermal runaway is completed, which is 1 hour, where the system burns completely, which finalizes the test. With the necessary protection, the extinction from the test is let to rest for the next 48 hours. The tests are recorded using the thermal camera to observe the thermal runaway propagation. A data logger is used to log the information of the temperatures and the voltage of the devices under test to study the temperature distribution during the entire process, and the test setup is photographed before and after the completion of the test for documentation and future references and analysis.

Figure 22: Thermal abuse test setup at cell level

3.1.2. Overcharge Test

The overcharge test is carried out to evaluate the behavior of the cell beyond its rated maximum voltage to check the safety risks and its effect on capacity degradation due to overvoltage. In this test, the SOC of the cell is set to 100 %, and the cell voltage is set to 4.84V, which is way higher than U_{max_safety} , and then a high current close to 1C is applied for 60 minutes with the cell temperature being at 15 °C. The parameters like cell voltage and temperatures are measured using a data logger. When the test is completed, the system is let to rest for the next 3 hours.

Figure 23: Front and top view of the cell overcharge test setup

Procedures like normal and thermal imaging to visualize and study the temperature distribution, physical deformation, and behavior of the cell during the test are used, through thermal and reflex cameras. The measurement of the cell voltage and the temperature are done before starting the overcharge test. After the test, once the rest period is completed the cell is removed from the test setup to inspect the physical damage due to the overcharging test followed by safe disposal of the cell.

3.1.3. Drop Test

The drop test is carried out to test the capability to withstand and the robustness of the cell during a mechanical impact while falling or a shock as a part of the crucial assessment to evaluate the risk factors like structural failure, leakage, and thermal runaway. Based on the UNECE R100 legislation for the drop test, the battery system is dropped from the height of 1 meter onto a rigid, flat, and unyielding surface to study the behavior of the cell after impact to assess the risk factors [Quelle].

Figure 24: Drop test setup at cell level

3.1.4. Impact Test

The impact test of the cell is done to assess the mechanical abuse of the cell to evaluate the withstanding capabilities of the cell in real-time operating conditions to validate the internal behavior of the devices under test and damage to its components due to impact on the outer surface. The test is carried out by placing the surface with the longest dimension on a flat and rigid surface, and a stainless-steel rod is being dropped from a height of 61 cm with a lower and higher tolerance of 2.5 cm. The impact rod has a weight limit of 9.1 kg with a 0.1 kg tolerance level, and it has a vertical sliding track about the horizontal surface where the cell is placed. The cell is impacted with its longitudinal axis to the flat surface and perpendicular to the longitudinal axis of 15.8 mm with a tolerance of 0.1 mm diameter with the surface layer across the centre of the test cell.

Figure 25: Impact test setup at cell level

3.1.5. Nail Penetration

The nail penetration test is designed to evaluate the safety of the cell in an internal short circuit event caused by the mechanical damage to the battery pack during vehicle crash, accidents and structural failure issues in the electric vehicle. The test cell is fully charged to 100 % SOC at the start of the test. It is placed lying on the widest part of the cell by placing horizontally in the testing equipment and the designated nail of the equipment, made of steel with 3-8 mm diameter is mounted and placed to move perpendicular to the cell's widest area at a speed of 10-50 mm per second. The penetration process is done using the gas compressor and continued until the nail completely passes through the cell. Then, the temperatures and voltages are monitored, and data is logged for the entire test duration using the data logger device. The thermal camera and the reflex camera are used to capture the test for documentation purposes. This test procedure is followed based on the UNECE R100 legislation for the validation of the cell in the safety limits of the legislation.

Figure 26: Nail penetration test setup at cell level

3.1.6. Crush Test

The crush test studies the behavior of the cell during a mechanical force applied to it, which results in the cell's deformation under real-world impact conditions, such as vehicle crash scenarios for the battery. It also studies and evaluates the risks of thermal runaway, internal short circuits, explosions, and fire conditions after the implications of the mechanical force.

The test cell is set to the SOC of 50 % before the test. To begin with the test, the cell is placed on the flat surfaces in the equipment, and the crushing force is applied to the widest part of the cell, so the cell has been placed horizontally to apply force uniformly over the cell for effectively studying the behavior of the cell. The mechanical force (pressure) is applied using a compressor to load the cell gradually, until it reaches 13 kN, and then it is held in this condition for a few minutes. Then the force is released, and the test cell is left to rest for a duration of 1 hour. Then the test is completed with the observation time for the cell behavior after the test, to see if there is any fire, explosion or venting of gases from the cell. The physical deformation of the cell is noted. Then, the temperatures and voltage are monitored, and data is logged for the entire test duration using the data logging device. The thermal camera and the reflex camera are used to capture the test for the documentation of the test. This crush test procedure is followed based on the UN 38.3 legislation for the validation of the cell in the safety limits of the legislation.

Figure 27: Crush test setup at cell level

3.2. Module level

At module level, the following safety-related tests are performed:

- thermal abuse test
- drop test
- impact test
- crush test

3.2.1. Thermal abuse test

The thermal abuse test is essential in the battery industry to evaluate the behavior of the module and their thermal stability at extremely high temperatures, which helps to assess safety risks like thermal runaway scenarios. The test case scenario for the MARBEL module is that the SOC of the cell is set to 50 %, the voltage and temperature measurement of the module is carried out before starting the test, when the test is initialized to reach a temperature of 100 °C. With the help

of the resistance cable (22wg) one cell in the center of the module is connected and voltage is supplied to it using a power source. and the test is initialized to reach a temperature of 100 °C. Once the temperature reaches 100 °C, then test is continued until the thermal runaway is triggered. When the thermal runaway is started, a rest phase is done until the thermal runaway and a potential propagation is completed, which is 1 hour, where the module burns completely, which finalizes the test. With the necessary protection, the extinction from the test is let to rest for the next 48 hours. The tests are recorded using the thermal camera to observe the thermal runaway propagation; a data logger is used to log the information of the temperatures and the voltage of the module to study the temperature distribution through the entire module during the process, and the test setup is photographed before and after the completion of the test for documentation and future references and analysis.

Figure 28: Thermal abuse test at module level

The thermal abuse test is conducted at module level with multiple thermocouples at different locations of the module to assess the temperature distribution in the module during thermal abuse test. The top cover lid on the module is removed to see if there is any internal short circuit and the module is painted black to see if there is any spark, fire or explosion in the cells during the test.

3.2.2. Drop test

The drop test is carried out to test the withstanding capabilities and robustness of the module for a mechanical impact in real world scenarios. The module is dropped to experience a shock as a part of the crucial assessment to evaluate the risk factors like structural failure, leakage, and thermal runaway. Based on the UNECE R100 legislation for the drop test, the device under test is dropped from the height of 1 meter onto a rigid, flat, and unyielding surface to study the behavior of the module while it experiences an impact to assess the risk factors. The drop test is carried out with the module and has a different setup when compared to the cell drop test by using more thermocouples to measure the temperature distribution across the module in between the cells and the BMS.

Figure 29: Drop test setup at module level

3.2.3. Impact Test

The major objective of the impact test at module level is to assess the mechanical abuse on the module to evaluate the capabilities of the module and the internal behavior of the devices under test and damage to its components due to impact on the outer surface. The test is carried out by placing the module with its surface with the longest dimension on a flat and rigid surface, and a stainless-steel rod is being dropped from a height of 61 cm with a lower and higher tolerance of 2.5 cm. The impact rod has a weight limit of 9.1 kg with a 0.1 kg tolerance level, and it has a vertical sliding track about the horizontal surface where the module is placed. The impact on the device with its longitudinal axis to the flat surface and perpendicular to the longitudinal axis of 15.8mm with a tolerance of 0.1 mm diameter with the surface layer across the centre of the test device.

The impact test setup differs slightly from the cell setup by using more thermocouples between the cells in the module device to measure the temperature distribution across the module and the BMS. Voltage and the temperature are measured before and after the test.

Figure 30: Impact test setup at module level and initial measurements before the test

3.2.4. Crush Test

The module crush test is conducted to validate the behavior of the module during the mechanical force (pressure) is applied to the DUT in the form of compression, which results in the physical deformation of the module in real-world scenarios, such as electric vehicle crash scenarios. It also studies and evaluates the risks of thermal runaway, internal short circuits, explosions, and fire conditions after the implications of the mechanical force.

The module is set to the SOC of 50 % before the test. To begin with the test, module is placed on the flat surfaces in the equipment, and the crushing force is applied to the widest part of the module, so the module is placed horizontally to apply force uniformly over the module for effectively studying the behavior of the module. The mechanical force (pressure) is applied using a compressor to load the module gradually, until it reaches 13 kN, and then it is held in this condition for a few minutes. Then the force is released, and the module is left to cool down for a duration of 1 hour. Then the test is completed with the observation for the module behavior after the test, to see if there is any short circuit, fire, explosion or venting of the gases from the module. The physical structure deformation of the module is observed. Then the temperatures and voltages are monitored, and data is logged for the entire test duration using the data logging device. The thermal camera and the reflex camera are used to capture the test for the documentation of the test. This crush test procedure is followed based on the UNECE R100 [3] legislation for the validation of the module in the safety limits of the legislation.

Figure 31: Crush test setup at module level

3.3. Pack Level (400 V System)

After conducting tests at cell and module level, extending the safety validation to the battery pack level is essential. While individual cells and modules provide valuable insights into performance and safety characteristics, the interactions between components within a fully assembled battery pack introduce additional complexities that require thorough testing. The pack-level safety validation ensures that all integrated safety mechanisms function correctly under various conditions, ultimately contributing to the overall reliability and safety of the battery system.

Battery packs differ significantly from individual cells and modules due to their increased complexity and the presence of additional safety systems such as fuses, contactors, insulation monitoring devices, warning peripherals, and BMS. Multiple cells and modules interact within a

structural housing at this level, incorporating cooling systems and protective enclosures. These factors introduce new potential failure modes that cannot be fully assessed at the cell or module level.

Testing at the pack level is crucial to evaluating the effectiveness of built-in safety measures and understanding the consequences of potential failures. Furthermore, it provides insights into the system's overall thermal behavior, electrical integrity, and mechanical stability under extreme conditions. This validation is essential for ensuring compliance with regulatory requirements and optimizing real-world application design; and finally to validate the initially defined requirements in MARBEL.

The primary objective of the pack-level safety validation is to assess the system's behavior in both normal and failure scenarios, focusing on the effectiveness of built-in safety mechanisms and the potential consequences of their failure. One essential aspect of testing is determining whether protective features such as fuses, contactors, insulation monitors, warning peripherals, and the BMS react appropriately to abnormal conditions. By applying specific abusive test conditions, the validation ensures that these components operate as intended, preventing hazardous situations such as thermal runaway or uncontrolled electrical faults.

Beyond verifying the effectiveness of safety mechanisms, the tests also investigate how the battery pack responds when these systems are intentionally deactivated or bypassed. For instance, in a short-circuit scenario where no fuse interrupts the current flow, it is critical to analyze which component fails first and how the overall system reacts. Similarly, testing the thermal management system under stress conditions provides insights into its ability to prevent overheating and mitigate the risk of thermal runaway/propagation. Since battery modules are composed of multiple interconnected cells, it is also important to examine how individual cells behave within the assembled pack and how the surrounding structure influences their performance. The BMS closely monitors these aspects, which records key parameters during each test scenario.

This section first presents and compares relevant standards for abusive testing to establish a solid basis for evaluating test results. Following this, the test plan is outlined, detailing the planned tests, conditions, and setups. Finally, the evaluation approach is described.

3.3.1. Standards for Abusive Testing of Battery Packs

3.3.1.1. Overview of Existing Standards and Included Abusive Tests

In the context of battery safety testing, various standards and regulatory frameworks have been developed to evaluate the robustness and reliability of battery systems under abusive conditions. This section examines and compares key standards that define abuse testing procedures for battery systems, specifically:

- **UNECE R100 Revision 3** – A globally recognized regulation addressing safety requirements for rechargeable energy storage systems (RESS) in electric vehicles [3].
- **SAE J2929-2013** – A standard developed by the Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) that sets safety criteria for lithium-based rechargeable energy storage systems in electric and hybrid-electric vehicles [5].
- **SAE J2464-2021** – An updated and comprehensive SAE standard detailing abuse testing procedures for lithium-ion battery systems [6].
- **GB 38031** – A Chinese national standard that establishes safety requirements for power batteries in electric vehicles, reflecting stringent safety considerations specific to the Chinese market [7].

Additionally, the **FreedomCAR [8]** initiative was reviewed, as it represents an early and foundational research effort that influenced many of the subsequent standards for battery safety testing. FreedomCAR, initiated in the early 2000s, provided fundamental guidelines for abuse testing, which have been adapted and refined in later industry and regulatory standards.

These standards were selected for analysis because they represent a diverse and internationally relevant set of guidelines covering different regulatory and industrial perspectives. UNECE R100 is critical for ensuring compliance with global vehicle safety regulations. The SAE standards (J2929 and J2464) are widely used in North America and provide detailed technical criteria for battery safety. GB 38031 is essential for understanding safety requirements in China, one of the largest electric vehicle markets in the world. By incorporating FreedomCAR, this analysis also accounts for the historical development of abuse testing methodologies and their evolution over time.

Abuse tests are generally categorized into electrical, mechanical, and thermal abuse tests, each addressing different failure mechanisms that can compromise battery safety. The following overview considers a selection of critical tests across these categories to evaluate the resilience of battery systems under extreme conditions.

- Electrical abuse tests, including Overcharge, Overdischarge and Recharge, and External Short Circuit, assess the effects of improper charging, excessive discharging, or electrical faults. These conditions can lead to dangerous consequences such as thermal runaway, internal short circuits, or irreversible capacity degradation.
- Mechanical abuse tests, such as Nail Penetration, Vibration, and Crush Test, evaluate the battery’s ability to withstand physical damage from punctures, impacts, or compressive forces. These tests simulate real-world mechanical stresses that could lead to internal short circuits or structural failure.
- Thermal abuse tests, particularly Overheating (Thermal Stability), examine the battery’s behavior under elevated temperatures to ensure stability and prevent thermal runaway in high-temperature environments.

The specific tests selected for this test plan – overcharge, overdischarge and recharge, external short circuit, overheating (thermal stability), nail penetration, crush and vibration test – were chosen because they represent the most critical failure scenarios that can arise from misuse, malfunctions, or external impacts. Their inclusion aligns with widely recognized regulatory and industry standards, ensuring a comprehensive battery safety and reliability assessment.

Table 3 provides an overview of which tests are covered by the selected standards. The standards generally show a high degree of overlap, with nearly every test included in each standard. The only two exceptions are the Nail Penetration Test, which UNECE R100 and SAE J2929 do not cover, and the Vibration Test, which is not included in FreedomCAR and SAE J2464.

Table 3: Overview of the described abuse tests in the respective standards. Included tests are marked with a tick (✓). If the field is empty, the standard does not cover the test.

	Over-charge	Overdis-charge + recharge	Exter-nal short circuit	Over-heating (Thermal stability)	Nail pene-tration	Crush	Vibration
Freedom CAR	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
UNECE R100 Revision 3	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓

SAE J2929-2013	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓
SAE J2464-2021	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
GB 38031-2020	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

3.3.1.2. Selection of Abusive Tests for Safety Validation

Two 400 V battery packs are planned to be subjected to abusive tests to evaluate their response under extreme conditions. The tests will be performed in two phases: first, with safety mechanisms enabled to assess their effectiveness, and then with safety mechanisms disabled to observe worst-case failure scenarios.

Phase 1: Tests with Safety Mechanisms Enabled

In the first phase, the functionality of the battery’s protective systems – such as fuses, contactors, and the Battery Management System (BMS) – will be evaluated under abuse conditions. The tests will be distributed across the two battery packs to optimize execution time, as certain tests, particularly overcharge and overdischarge, require extended durations.

Before conducting any electrical or thermal abuse tests, Pack 2 will first undergo a vibration test to assess its structural integrity and ensure that no damage occurs that could influence subsequent tests.

Pack 1: Overcharge, Overheat, and Short Circuit

Pack 2: Vibration, Overdischarge and Recharge

This distribution has been chosen due to the tests' differing time requirements. Overcharge and over-discharge are among the longest-running tests, so separating them across the two packs allows for parallel execution and more efficient use of testing time. The results of this phase will indicate whether the integrated safety features successfully prevent hazardous failures.

Phase 2: Tests with Safety Mechanisms Disabled

In the second phase, safety mechanisms will be bypassed to observe the battery packs' behavior under extreme conditions without intervention. The objective is to evaluate their failure modes and determine the likelihood of thermal runaway.

Pack 1: Overcharge → (if no thermal runaway occurs) Short Circuit → (if still no thermal runaway) Nail Penetration

Pack 2: Overheat

The test sequence for Pack 1 is designed to escalate stress conditions progressively. If the battery withstands the overcharge test without thermal runaway, it will be subjected to a short circuit. If it remains stable, a nail penetration test will be conducted to induce an internal short circuit and provoke a thermal runaway. However, depending on the results of each step, the test series may conclude earlier if failure occurs.

Overheat testing has been selected for Pack 2 due to its prolonged duration and the expectation that the test will permanently damage the battery pack.

Crush testing will not be performed as it is not feasible to conduct at the battery pack level.

3.3.1.3. Description and Comparison of Standards Regarding the Selected Abusive Tests

The following describes and compares the selected abuse tests (all except Crush) based on the standards outlined in section 3.3.1.1.

Table 4 provides a detailed comparison of the **Overcharge** test settings and procedures across the selected standards. It highlights the differences and similarities in general test conditions, device under test preparation, charging procedures, and passing requirements.

Table 4: Comparison of overcharge test settings and procedures across standards

Standard	Test Settings	Test Procedure
FreedomCAR	Temp: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Normal operating temp SOC: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100% DUT Preparation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inside standard container, cooling active 	Charge: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Constant current of 32 A, voltage limit of 450 V • Continue charging until: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 200% SOC - 4 hours - Failure (as agreed with manufacturer) After: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitor and record for 2 hours post-charging Passing Requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No fire, no explosion, no rupture
UNECE R100 Rev. 3	Temp: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 °C ± 10 °C SOC: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Middle of normal range DUT Preparation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protection devices active • Main contactor closed 	Charge: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Charge via external power source, charge control limits disabled • Charge at max manufacturer-specified current Stop at: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overcharge protection activates - Temperature exceeds max operating temp by 10 °C - If no cut-off, stop after 12 hours After: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct standard cycle if permitted • Observe for 1 hour at ambient temp Passing Requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No fire, no explosion, no hazardous failure
SAE J2929-2013	Temp: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 25 °C ± 5 °C SOC: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 95-100% DUT Preparation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooling system active if required • Active charge control disabled 	Charge: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Charge at max possible rate for application • Voltage limit set by charge device output Stop at: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Charge device reaches voltage limit • Connection interface disconnects battery from charger After: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observe for 1 hour, monitor for flammable gas leakage Passing Requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No fire, no explosion, no enclosure

		rupture, no venting (verified visually or with gas detection)
SAE J2464-2021	<p>Temp:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> nominal operating temperature <p>SOC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 100% <p>DUT Preparation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Passive overcharge protection active Active protection disabled 	<p>Charge:</p> <p>Modules & Packs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Charge at 1C If pack < 400V: 150% of max charge voltage If pack ≥ 400V: 120% of max charge voltage Stop at 200% SOC or destructive termination <p>After:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use Section 4.1.5 for hazard evaluation <p>Passing Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> No fire, no explosion, assess hazard severity level
GB 38031-2020	<p>Temp: 20 °C ± 10 °C (or higher if requested)</p> <p>SOC: Middle of the normal operating range</p> <p>DUT Preparation: Protection devices active, main contactors closed, pretreatment cycle applied before test</p>	<p>Charge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> External charging equipment connected to DUT main terminals Charge control limits disabled Use shortest charging strategy approved by manufacturer <p>Stop at:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> DUT automatically terminates charging DUT sends termination signal If no termination, continue until DUT temp exceeds max operating temp by 10 °C If temp remains below this threshold, continue for 12 hours <p>After:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Observe for 1 hour at ambient temp <p>Passing Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> No leakage, housing cracks, fire, or explosion Insulation resistance must be at least 100 Ohm/V

The following differences between the tests, as outlined in the table, can be identified based on the respective standards:

General Test Conditions

UNECE R100 and GB 38031-2020 specify a test temperature of 20 ± 10 °C, while SAE J2929 requires 25 ± 5 °C. Both FreedomCAR and SAE J2464 define a normal/nominal operating temperature.

State of charge before testing varies between the standards. FreedomCAR and SAE J2464 require a fully charged battery at 100 % SOC, while UNECE R100 and GB 38031-2020 adjust the SOC to the middle of the normal operating range. SAE J2929 specifies 95 to 100 % SOC before testing.

DUT Preparation

All standards require that normal protection devices are operational before testing. GB 38031-2020 and UNECE R100 mandate that the main contactors remain closed. SAE J2929 requires active charge control to be disabled, while SAE J2464 requires active protection to be disabled while maintaining passive protection. FreedomCAR and SAE J2929 ensure that the cooling system operates during the test.

Test Procedure

UNECE R100 and GB 38031-2020 use external charging equipment with no charge control limits, charging at the maximum current specified by the manufacturer. GB 38031-2020 allows charging to continue under certain conditions until 12 hours have passed. FreedomCAR overcharges at a fixed 32 A up to 450 V, stopping at 200 percent SOC or after 4 hours. SAE J2929 follows a similar principle but stops charging when the connection interface disconnects the battery. SAE J2464 differentiates between low- and high-voltage battery packs, with different termination criteria based on maximum voltage or SOC.

Passing Requirements

All standards require the battery system to show no fire, explosion, or hazardous failures. UNECE R100, SAE J2929, and GB 38031-2020 include a post-test observation period of at least 1 hour, while FreedomCAR monitors for 2 hours. SAE J2929 also requires visual inspection of venting and gas measurement. GB 38031-2020 includes additional criteria prohibiting leakage, housing cracks, and requiring an insulation resistance of at least 100 Ohm/V.

Table 5 compares the **Overdischarge and Recharge** test settings and procedures across the selected standards in the same manner as Table 4.

Table 5: Comparison of over discharge test settings and procedures across standards.

Standard	Test Settings	Test Procedure
FreedomCAR	<p>Temp:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Normal operating temp <p>SOC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100% <p>DUT Preparation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooling system active • Passive overdischarge protection enabled • Non-passive protections disabled 	<p>Discharge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discharge at C/1 rate <p>Stop at:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1.5 hours elapsed • 50% of subassemblies show voltage reversal for 15 minutes <p>After:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observe DUT for additional period <p>Passing Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No fire, no explosion, no hazardous failure
UNECE R100 Rev. 3	<p>Temp:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 °C ± 10 °C <p>SOC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low level in normal range <p>DUT Preparation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protection devices active • Main contactor closed 	<p>Discharge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perform discharge at stable current within manufacturer-specified range <p>Stop at:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DUT automatically terminates discharge • Temperature stabilizes with less than 4 °C variation in 2 hours • If no termination, discharge until DUT reaches 25% of nominal voltage <p>After:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct a standard charge-discharge cycle if not inhibited • Observe for 1 hour at ambient temp <p>Passing Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No fire, no explosion, no hazardous event
SAE J2929-2013	<p>Temp:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 25 °C ± 5 °C 	<p>Discharge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HEV/PHEV: 1C rate

	<p>SOC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 95-100% <p>DUT Preparation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooling system active if required • Battery Control Function manages interface • Passive protection active • Active discharge control disabled 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EV: C/3 rate <p>Stop at:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connection interface disconnects • Battery voltage reaches $0.0\text{ V} \pm 0.2\text{ V}$ <p>After:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observe for 1 hour, monitor for flammable gas leakage <p>Passing Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No fire, no explosion, no enclosure rupture, no venting (verified visually or with gas detection)
SAE J2464-2021	<p>Temp:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • nominal operating temperature <p>SOC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100% <p>DUT Preparation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active protections disabled • passive overdischarge protection active 	<p>Discharge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discharge a completely discharged cell in series with fully charged cells • Parallel connected cells treated as a single unit • Discharge at max recommended current until module voltage reaches $0.0\text{ V} \pm 0.2\text{ V}$ • Maintain 0.0 V for 30 minutes <p>After:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observe for at least 60 minutes post-test <p>Passing Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No fire, no explosion, assess hazard severity level
GB 38031-2020	<p>Temp:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ <p>SOC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low level in normal range <p>DUT Preparation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protection devices active • Main contactors closed • pretreatment cycle applied before test 	<p>Discharge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connect external discharging equipment to DUT main terminals • Discharge at stable current as negotiated with manufacturer <p>Stop at:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DUT automatically terminates discharge • DUT sends termination signal • If no termination, continue discharge until DUT reaches 25% of rated voltage • If temperature stabilizes with variation less than $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ over 2 hours <p>After:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observe for 1 hour at ambient temp <p>Passing Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No leakage, housing cracks, fire, or explosion • Insulation resistance must be at least 100 Ohm/V

General Test Conditions

GB 38031-2020 and UNECE R100 specify an ambient temperature of $20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, while SAE J2929 requires $25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ unless a more severe condition is chosen. FreedomCAR and SAE J2464 use nominal operating temperature. SOC levels differ, with FreedomCAR and SAE J2464 requiring 100 % SOC, UNECE R100 and GB 38031-2020 setting SOC at a lower level within the normal range, and SAE J2929 requiring 95-100 % SOC.

DUT Preparation

All standards keep the DUT in normal operating conditions, but only SAE J2464 and FreedomCAR disable active protective devices while maintaining passive overdischarge protection. GB 38031-2020 includes a pretreatment cycle, while FreedomCAR and SAE J2929 ensure cooling systems remain operational if they would normally function during discharge.

Test Procedure

FreedomCAR discharges at a C/1 rate and stops after 1.5 hours or when 50 % of subassemblies reach voltage reversal. UNECE R100 and GB 38031-2020 use a stable discharge current and terminate when the DUT stops discharge, temperature stabilizes, or voltage drops to 25 % of nominal. SAE J2929 uses a 1C rate for HEV/PHEV and C/3 for EV, stopping at $0.0\text{ V} \pm 0.2\text{ V}$ or disconnection. SAE J2464 discharges a fully discharged cell in series with fully charged cells, maintaining $0.0\text{ V} \pm 0.2\text{ V}$ for 30 minutes.

Passing Requirements

All standards require the battery system to show no fire, explosion, or hazardous failures. UNECE R100, SAE J2929, and GB 38031-2020 include a post-test observation period of at least 1 hour, while FreedomCAR does not specify a post-test requirement. SAE J2929 also requires visual inspection of venting and gas measurement. GB 38031-2020 includes additional criteria prohibiting leakage, housing cracks, and requiring an insulation resistance of at least 100 Ohm/V.

Table 6 compares the **External Short Circuit** test settings and procedures across the selected standards in the same manner as the tables before.

Table 6: Comparison of external short circuit test settings and procedures across standards.

Standard	Test Settings	Test Procedure
FreedomCAR	<p>Temp:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nominal operating temperature <p>SOC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 100% <p>DUT Preparation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Passive short circuit protection enabled, all non-passive protective devices disabled 	<p>Short Circuit:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply a hard short using a conductor $\leq 5\text{ m}\Omega$ in less than 1 second If DUT has $\leq 5\text{ m}\Omega$ internal resistance, use a conductor of 1/10 DUT resistance <p>Stop at:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 10 minutes elapsed Another failure condition prevents completion (e.g., component melting) <p>After:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Observe for 2 hours <p>Passing Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> No fire, no explosion, no hazardous failure
UNECE R100 Rev. 3	<p>Temp:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> $20\text{ }^\circ\text{C} \pm 10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ <p>SOC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 95-100% <p>DUT Preparation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> All protection devices active main contactors closed 	<p>Short Circuit:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connect positive and negative terminals with resistance $\leq 5\text{ m}\Omega$ If testing with a full vehicle, apply short via breakout harness <p>Stop at:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Protection system terminates short-circuit current Temperature stabilizes with variation less than $4\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ over 2 hours, then continue short circuit for 1 hour <p>After:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct a standard cycle if not inhibited Observe for 1 hour at ambient temp <p>Passing Requirements:</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No fire, no explosion, no hazardous event
SAE J2929-2013	<p>Temp:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 25 °C ± 5 °C (or more severe condition) <p>SOC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 95-100% <p>DUT Preparation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Battery system in operational state, protection devices not bypassed 	<p>Short Circuit:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Follow SAE J2464 <p>Stop at:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Follow SAE J2464 <p>After:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Observe for 1 hour, monitor for flammable gas leakage <p>Passing Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> No fire, no explosion, no enclosure rupture, no venting (verified visually or with gas detection)
SAE J2464-2021	<p>Temp:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nominal operating temperature <p>SOC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 100% <p>DUT Preparation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Active protections disabled before test 	<p>Short Circuit:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply a hard short ($\leq 5 \text{ m}\Omega$) between DUT terminals in less than 1 second Soft short test also performed with resistance no less than 10 mΩ <p>Stop at:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 60 minutes elapsed Another condition prevents completion (e.g., fuse open, component melting) <p>After:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Observe for 1 hour Hazard severity level determined per Section 4.1.5 <p>Passing Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> No fire, no explosion, assess hazard severity level
GB 38031-2020	<p>Temp:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 20 °C ± 10 °C (or higher if requested) <p>SOC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not specified <p>DUT Preparation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Protection devices active main contactors closed 	<p>Short Circuit:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connect positive and negative terminals with resistance $\leq 5 \text{ m}\Omega$ <p>Stop at:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Protection function activates and terminates short-circuit current If temperature stabilizes with variation less than 4 °C in 2 hours, continue short circuit for 1 hour <p>After:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Observe for 1 hour at ambient temp <p>Passing Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> No leakage, housing cracks, fire, or explosion Insulation resistance must be at least 100 Ohm/V

General Test Conditions

GB 38031-2020 and UNECE R100 specify an ambient temperature of 20 °C ± 10 °C, while FreedomCAR, SAE J2929, and SAE J2464 operate at nominal operating temperature. SOC levels also differ. FreedomCAR and SAE J2464 require 100 % SOC, while UNECE R100 sets the SOC at 95-100 %. GB 38031-2020 does not specify a SOC level.

DUT Preparation

All standards require the DUT to be in normal operating conditions, but only SAE J2464, SAE J2929, and FreedomCAR disable active protection devices while keeping passive short circuit protection enabled. UNECE R100 and GB 38031-2020 require all protection systems to be active.

GB 38031-2020 and UNECE R100 also specify that all main contactors must be closed before the test.

Test Procedure

FreedomCAR applies a hard short using a conductor with a resistance of 5 mΩ or less. If the DUT has an internal resistance of 5 mΩ or less, the conductor must have a resistance equal to one-tenth of the DUT's minimum resistance. UNECE R100 and GB 38031-2020 apply a short circuit using a connection with a resistance of 5 mΩ or less. SAE J2464 and SAE J2929 apply both a hard short of 5 mΩ or less and a soft short of at least 10 mΩ. The test duration varies, with FreedomCAR stopping after 10 minutes or earlier if a failure occurs. SAE J2464 and SAE J2929 run for 60 minutes unless a condition such as fuse opening or component melting prevents completion. UNECE R100 and GB 38031-2020 continue until the protection function activates or temperature stabilizes, after which the short circuit must continue for an additional hour.

Passing Requirements

All standards require no fire, explosion, or rupture. UNECE R100 and GB 38031-2020 require a minimum 1-hour observation period after testing, while FreedomCAR mandates 2 hours. SAE J2929 requires additional gas measurement for flammability. GB 38031-2020 has an added requirement of maintaining insulation resistance above 100 Ohm/V post-test.

Table 7 compares the **Overheating (Thermal Stability)** test settings and procedures across the selected standards in the same manner as the tables before.

Table 7: Comparison of overheating (thermal stability) test settings and procedures across standards.

Standard	Test Settings	Test Procedure
FreedomCAR	<p>Temp:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Normal operating temperature <p>SOC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100% <p>DUT Preparation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passive protections enabled, • non-passive protective devices disabled 	<p>Heating:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase temperature in increments • Use near-adiabatic environment if possible • Conduct ARC test, increasing temperature from 30°C to 200°C at 10°C/min, holding for 120 minutes per step <p>Stop at:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-heating detection with stable exotherm • 200°C above operating temperature • Catastrophic event (e.g., venting, major damage) <p>If thermal runaway occurs, repeat test with 2°C increments</p> <p>After:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No specified observation period <p>Passing Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No fire, no explosion, no hazardous failure
UNECE R100 Rev. 3	<p>Temp:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 °C ± 10 °C (or higher if requested) <p>SOC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not specified <p>DUT Preparation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protection devices active, • cooling system disable 	<p>Heating:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Place DUT in convective oven or climatic chamber • Gradually increase temperature until reaching one of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Operational temperature threshold for protection systems - Maximum operational temperature if no internal protection exists <p>Continue heating until:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DUT limits charge/discharge to

		<p>prevent temperature increase</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Temperature stabilizes with less than 4 °C variation over 2 hours <p>After:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observe for 1 hour <p>Passing Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No fire, no explosion, no hazardous event
SAE J2929-2013	<p>Temp:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nominal operating temperature <p>SOC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100% <p>DUT Preparation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooling system disabled • battery control function active 	<p>Heating:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct test per SAE J2464 Section 4.4.3 • Perform full charge and discharge cycles • Charge at maximum normal rate <p>Stop at:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overtemperature conditions lead to system failure <p>After:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observe for 1 hour • Monitor for flammable gas using a spark source or gas concentration device <p>Passing Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No fire, no explosion, no enclosure rupture, no hazardous gas concentration
SAE J2464-2021	<p>Temp:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nominal operating temperature <p>SOC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100% <p>DUT Preparation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DUT uninsulated, exposed to static air conditions 	<p>Heating:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ramp rate: $\geq 5^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ • Increase temperature in 5°C increments, holding for 30 minutes per step <p>Continue until:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Self-heating is detected ($>1.0^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$) - DUT reaches 300°C above operating temperature - Catastrophic event occurs <p>After:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observe for 1 hour <p>Passing Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No fire, no explosion, assess hazard severity level
GB 38031-2020	<p>Temp:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $20^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 10^{\circ}\text{C}$ (or higher if requested) <p>SOC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not specified <p>DUT Preparation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protection devices active • cooling system disabled 	<p>Heating:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Charge and discharge DUT to increase temperature as quickly as possible <p>Gradually raise chamber temperature until:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DUT reaches temperature for protection system activation - If no protection system, DUT reaches max manufacturer-specified temperature <p>Maintain temperature until:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DUT stops or limits charge/discharge - Temperature stabilizes with variation of less than 4°C over 2 hours <p>After:</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observe for 1 hour <p>Passing Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No fire, no explosion, no hazardous event • No leakage, no housing crack • Insulation resistance after test must be at least 100 Ohm/V
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General Test Conditions

GB 38031-2020 and UNECE R100 specify an ambient temperature of 20 °C ± 10 °C, while FreedomCAR, SAE J2929, and SAE J2464 operate at nominal operating temperature. FreedomCAR, SAE J2929, and SAE J2464 require the DUT to be fully charged at 100 % SOC, while UNECE R100 and GB 38031-2020 do not specify a required SOC level.

DUT Preparation

All standards require the DUT to be in a normal operational state, but UNECE R100 and GB 38031-2020 require the cooling system to be disabled, while FreedomCAR and SAE J2929 test the system under normal conditions with protections active. SAE J2464 places the DUT in an uninsulated, static air environment to simulate worst-case thermal conditions.

Test Procedure

The heating process and termination criteria vary between the standards. FreedomCAR uses an ARC test, ramping from 30 °C to 200 °C at 10 °C/min and holding for 120 minutes per step. SAE J2464 ramps at a minimum of 5 °C/min, increasing in 5 °C increments and holding for 30 minutes per step. UNECE R100 and GB 38031-2020 gradually increase temperature until reaching either an overtemperature protection threshold or a manufacturer-defined limit, while SAE J2929 follows the test method from SAE J2464, simulating failure of the battery's thermal control system. FreedomCAR and SAE J2464 continue testing until a catastrophic event, self-heating detection, or an extreme temperature limit is reached. UNECE R100 and GB 38031-2020 terminate the test once the DUT stops or limits charge/discharge, or temperature stabilizes within a 4 °C range over two hours.

Passing Requirements

All standards prohibit fire, explosion, or hazardous failures. SAE J2929 includes an additional requirement that no enclosure rupture or hazardous gas concentration is detected. SAE J2464 performs a hazard severity assessment, while UNECE R100 and GB 38031-2020 require a one-hour observation period at ambient conditions after the test. FreedomCAR does not specify a defined post-test observation period. GB 38031-2020 further requires no leakage, no housing cracks, and that insulation resistance after the test remains at least 100 Ohm/V.

Table 8 compares the **Nail Penetration** test settings and procedures across the selected standards in the same manner as the tables before.

Table 8: Comparison of nail penetration test settings and procedures across standards.

Standard	Test Settings	Test Procedure
FreedomCAR	<p>Temp:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not specified <p>SOC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not specified <p>DUT Preparation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electrically insulate the rod from the test article 	<p>Penetration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use a mild steel conductive pointed rod • Diameter: 20 mm • Rate of penetration: 8 cm/s • Depth: Through three units or 100 mm • Orientation: Perpendicular to electrode plates

		Passing Requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not specified
UNECE R100 Rev. 3	Not specified	Not specified
SAE J2929-2013	Not specified	Not specified
SAE J2464-2021	Temp: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nominal operating temperature SOC: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100% DUT Preparation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooling medium in place if applicable 	Penetration: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use a mild steel conductive rod • Diameter: 20 mm • Rod end type: Tapered to a sharp point • Rate of penetration: ≥ 8 cm/s • Depth: Through three cells or 100 mm, whichever is greater • Orientation: Perpendicular to electrode plates After: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observe for at least 1 hour with rod left in place • Hazard severity level determined per Section 4.1.5 Passing Requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not specified
GB 38031-2020	Temp: Not specified SOC: Not specified DUT Preparation: Protection devices removed if necessary	Penetration: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Needling material: Steel • Diameter: 3 mm - 8 mm • Shape: Conical, 20° - 60° angle • Speed: 0.1 mm/s - 10 mm/s • Position: Near center of pack or in a location likely to trigger thermal runaway • Orientation: Perpendicular to pole piece Passing Requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not specified

General Test Conditions

FreedomCAR and SAE J2464 require penetration testing under normal conditions but do not specify a set temperature. SAE J2464 explicitly requires the device under test to be fully charged at 100 % SOC, whereas FreedomCAR does not specify a SOC level. UNECE R100 and SAE J2929 do not define a nail penetration test.

DUT Preparation

SAE J2464 and FreedomCAR require the use of a conductive mild steel rod, with SAE J2464 specifying that the rod must be tapered to a sharp point. GB 38031-2020 allows a range of needle diameters between 3 mm and 8 mm and a conical shape with an angle between 20 and 60 degrees. Additionally, GB 38031-2020 recommends selecting a penetration position most likely to trigger thermal runaway, while SAE J2464 mandates penetration perpendicular to the electrode plates.

Test Procedure

FreedomCAR and SAE J2464 use a rod with a 20 mm diameter, penetrating at a rate of 8 cm per second through three cells or 100 mm, whichever is greater. GB 38031-2020 specifies a needle diameter between 3 mm and 8 mm and a penetration speed ranging from 0.1 mm per second to 10 mm per second, making it more adaptable but potentially leading to varying test results. GB

38031-2020 also explicitly targets thermal runaway initiation, whereas the other standards focus on general nail penetration.

Passing Requirements

SAE J2464 requires an observation period of at least one hour, with the rod left in place. It also mandates a hazard severity assessment, while FreedomCAR does not define post-test conditions. GB 38031-2020 does not specify detailed passing criteria for fire or explosion but emphasizes selecting conditions most likely to trigger thermal runaway.

Table 9 compares the **Vibration** test settings and procedures across the selected standards in the same manner as the tables before.

Table 9: Comparison of vibration settings and procedures across standards.

Standard	Test Settings	Test Procedure
FreedomCAR	Not specified	Not specified
UNECE R100 Rev. 3	<p>Temp:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 22 ± 5 °C <p>SOC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 95-100% <p>DUT Preparation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Device firmly secured to vibration platform using original mounting points 	<p>Vibration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sinusoidal waveform with logarithmic sweep between 7 Hz and 50 Hz, back to 7 Hz in 15 minutes • Repeat cycle 12 times for a total of 3 hours in vertical direction • Acceleration levels: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 7 to 18 Hz: 10 m/s² • 18 to 30 Hz: gradually reduced from 10 to 2 m/s² • 30 to 50 Hz: 2 m/s² • Manufacturer may request higher acceleration and frequency levels <p>After:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct a standard cycle if not inhibited • Observe for 1 hour at ambient temperature <p>Passing Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No fire, no explosion, no hazardous failure
SAE J2929-2013	<p>Temp:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not specified <p>SOC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 95-100% <p>DUT Preparation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full battery system tested 	<p>Vibration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Test performed according to UN Test Manual Test T.3, SAE J2380, or a customized profile reflecting actual application • Battery must remain operational throughout test <p>After:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observe for 1 hour • Measure open circuit voltage, must be at least 90 percent of pre-test value • Check high voltage isolation, must be at least 100 Ohm/V • No cracked, damaged, or loosened high-voltage conductors <p>Passing Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No fire, no explosion, no venting outside enclosure, no enclosure rupture
SAE J2464-2021	Not specified	Not specified

GB 38031-2020	<p>Temp:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not specified <p>SOC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 50 percent of the normal operating range <p>DUT Preparation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installed on vibration table per GB/T 2423.43 	<p>Vibration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply random and constant-frequency loads in x, y, and z directions • Sequence: z-axis random, z-axis constant-frequency, y-axis random, y-axis constant-frequency, x-axis random, x-axis constant-frequency • Parameters as stated in section 8.2.1.6 <p>After:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitor internal voltage and temperature during test • Observe for 2 hours at ambient temperature <p>Passing Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No fire, no explosion, no leakage, no housing crack • No abnormal termination • Insulation resistance must be at least 100 Ohm/V
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General Test Conditions

UNECE R100 specifies a test temperature of 22 ± 5 °C, while GB 38031-2020 does not define a test temperature but requires at least 50 % SOC before testing. SAE J2929 does not set an explicit test temperature but requires the battery to be charged to between 95 and 100 % of its maximum operating SOC.

DUT Preparation

UNECE R100 requires the device to be securely mounted on a vibration platform, preferably using its original mounting points. GB 38031-2020 follows a similar approach but requires installation according to GB/T 2423.43. SAE J2929 specifies that the entire battery system should be tested rather than individual modules, while UNECE R100 allows for subsystem testing if it can be demonstrated that the results are representative of the full system.

Test Procedure

UNECE R100 applies a sinusoidal vibration ranging from 7 Hz to 50 Hz, cycled 12 times over 3 hours, with acceleration levels between 2 and 10 meters per second squared. SAE J2929 follows either UN Test Manual Test T.3, SAE J2380, or a customized profile, allowing flexibility in vibration profiles. GB 38031-2020 applies random and constant-frequency loads in multiple directions, covering x, y, and z axes, with parameters as stated in section 8.2.1.6. of the standard

Passing Requirements

All standards prohibit fire, explosion, or hazardous failures. UNECE R100 and SAE J2929 require a one-hour observation period after the test, while GB 38031-2020 mandates a two-hour observation period. SAE J2929 also requires post-test verification of open circuit voltage, insulation resistance of at least 100 Ohm/V, and structural integrity of high-voltage conductors. GB 38031-2020 further specifies no leakage or housing cracks and an insulation resistance of at least 100 Ohm/V.

3.3.2. Approach to Abusive Testing of 400 V-packs

Since the UNECE R100 is globally recognized, it is used as the basis for all planned tests. For the nail penetration test, which is not covered by UNECE R100, FreedomCAR is employed as a basis.

3.3.2.1. Outline of General Testplan

As described above, tests are to be carried out at pack level to check the functionality of the safety systems in the event of abnormal operating conditions, hereafter referred to as *tests with safety mechanisms enabled*. Furthermore, tests are to be carried out to determine the behavior of the pack under abnormal operating conditions and in the event of failure of the safety systems, hereafter referred to as *tests with safety mechanisms disabled*.

Table 10 and Table 11 show the test schedule of all tests that are to be carried out at the testing sites of Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt, including all necessary preparation and follow-up steps. It is assumed here that both 400 V battery packs are delivered before 10.02.2025, as the table reflects the minimum time required for testing both packs before the end of the project period on 31.03.2025. The vibration test is not included in this overview, as this test cannot be carried out by Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt due to lack of the equipment needed for this test. For this reason, the vibration test is carried out on pack 2 by a third party before the pack arrives at Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt.

Table 10: Outline of the testplan for two 400 V-battery-packs, part 1 (dating from 10.02.2025 to 26.02.2025). (w s) indicates that a test is carried out with enabled safety mechanisms, (w/o s) shows that a test is performed with disabled safety mechanisms.

KW 7					KW 8					KW 9		
10.02.	11.02.	12.02.	13.02.	14.02.	17.02.	18.02.	19.02.	20.02.	21.02.	24.02.	25.02.	26.02.
Mo	Di	Mi	Do	Fr	Mo	Di	Mi	Do	Fr	Mo	Di	Mi
Preparation of Pack 1					Tests with Pack 1 with safety measures					Tests with Pack 1 with and without safety measures		
attach temperature, voltage etc. sensors										transport battery to abuse area prepare area for tests		
	insert high voltage interface						prepare overcharge test					prepare short circuit execute short circuit (w s) prepare overcharge execute overcharge (w/o s)
			prepare BMS temperature sensor and drill hole in battery pack's housing for nail					execute overcharge test (w s)				prepare short circuit execute short circuit (w/o s) prepare nail execute nail (w/o s)
	adapt nail penetration device to battery housing				establish communication with BMS				prepare overheating test, execute overheating test (w s)			
					prepare CaCl-water-solution							
Preparation of Pack 2					Tests with Pack 2 with safety measures					Tests with Pack 2 with and without safety measures		
attach temperature, voltage etc. sensors										transport battery to abuse area prepare area for tests		
		insert high voltage interface					prepare overdischarge test					blocker for tests with pack 1
					establish communication with BMS			execute overdischarge test (w s)				prepare overheat execute overheat (w/o s)

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Table 11: Outline of the testplan for two 400 V-battery-packs, part 2 (dating from 27.02.2025 to 31.03.2025). (w s) indicates that a test is carried out with enabled safety mechanisms, (w/o s) shows that a test is performed with disabled safety mechanisms.

27.02. Do	28.02. Fr	KW 10					KW 11					KW 12					KW 13					31.03. Mo	
		03.03. Mo	04.03. Di	05.03. Mi	06.03. Do	07.03. Fr	10.03. Mo	11.03. Di	12.03. Mi	13.03. Do	14.03. Fr	17.03. Mo	18.03. Di	19.03. Mi	20.03. Do	21.03. Fr	24.03. Mo	25.03. Di	26.03. Mi	27.03. Do	28.03. Fr		
Deactivation of Pack 1 in Salt Water		Transport to SK TES																					
Recycling of Battery and Waste Water																						End of Project	
sample collection waste water and analytics of samples																							
																			pickup and recycling of wastewater				
																			invoicing				
Deactivation of Pack 2 in Salt Water		Transport to SK TES																					
Recycling of Battery and Waste Water																							
sample collection waste water and analytics of samples																							
																			pickup and recycling of wastewater				
																			invoicing				

The general preparation and post-processing of the battery packs and testing areas are described below. Furthermore, a detailed presentation of the individual tests is given. For each test, the aim of the test, the planned procedure and the deviation from the standard on which the test is based are addressed.

3.3.2.2. General Preparation of Battery Packs and Testing Areas

Preparation of Packs

The type K **thermocouples**, which are installed in the packs to be tested, are of particular interest for the tests in which a thermal runaway is targeted. This is used to analyze the development and spread of the thermal runaway. Figure 32 shows the positioning of the thermocouples. 40 thermocouples are installed in the pack with the heatpads and 36 thermocouples are installed in the pack without heatpads.

Figure 32: Positioning of type K thermocouples (TCs) in the 400 V pack based on the example of the pack in which the heatpads for the overheat test are installed.

A **high-voltage interface** with two connection options is provided for power supply: For all tests with active safety mechanisms, a cable with a connector plug is assembled which fits into the socket provided in the pack housing. For all tests with deactivated safety mechanisms, the safety box (see Figure 32, black box) must be bypassed. For this purpose, the cable is fitted with cable lugs so that it can be connected to the contacts downstream of the safety box.

Communication with the BMS, among other things for reading out the temperature and voltage data of each individual cell, is realized via the SavvyCAN software.

For the nail penetration test on pack 1, the **nail penetration device** is adapted to the housing of pack 1 and a hole is drilled in the housing of pack 1 so that the nail can be inserted into the designated cell.

For the overheat test with deactivated safety mechanisms, **heatpads** are installed on one cell in pack 2. The positioning and installation of the heatpads can be seen in Figure 33 and Figure 34.

Position of heatpads: on a cell in the middle of a module in the middle of the pack

Figure 33: Positioning of heatpads in the 400 V pack.

Front view: 2 headpads, overlapping

Side view: 2 headpads on each side, overall 4 heatpads

Figure 34: Installation plan of heatpads, surrounding a single cell.

Preparation of Testing Areas

The tests are carried out at two different locations: Tests where the risk of thermal runaway is very low are carried out in a laboratory. Tests in which a thermal runaway is imaginable or is even the aim of the test are tested in a designated outdoor area.

For the tests in the **laboratory**, the battery pack is placed in a thermal chamber that can be flooded in the unlikely event of a thermal runaway.

The battery pack is placed in a tray during the tests on the **open area**. This tray must allow the pack to be completely flooded with a pre-prepared CaCl₂-water solution, as after the destructive tests on the open area the now potentially hazardous battery pack must be deactivated before it can be examined and/or disposed of. All equipment, such as measuring devices, must be placed at least 10 m away from this tray, unless it can be protected by shields or the like so that it is not destroyed by fire and/or heat in the event of a thermal runaway.

The testing equipment and measuring equipment is set up before each test. This includes

- the connection to the BMS of the pack
- the high-voltage harness to connect the pack to the power source
- an ICPDAS data acquisition system for additional sensors like the type K thermocouples
- prolongations for the type K sensors to be able to place the ICPDAS at least 10 m far away from the battery pack
- 2 video cameras
- 2 infrared cameras
- a weather station for the tests carried out on the open testing area
- a power supply unit (for overcharge and overdischarge tests with safety mechanisms enabled as well as for the heatpads in the overheat test with safety mechanisms disabled)
- a blowdryer (for overheat test with safety mechanisms enabled)
- a contactor (for the external short circuit tests with safety mechanisms enabled and disabled)
- the nail penetration device (for the nail penetration test)
- a cryostat equipped with coolant and hoses to connect it to the cooling channels of the pack (for the overheat test with safety mechanisms disabled)
- equipment for extinguishing and flooding the battery packs

The measuring equipment and the data to be recorded are covered in more detail in chapter 3.3.3.

3.3.2.3. Detailed Procedure of each Test

3.3.2.3.1. Tests with Safety Mechanisms Enabled

3.3.2.3.1.1. Vibration (Pack 2)

Aim A vibration test is used to determine whether the structural integrity of the battery pack is compromised due to the vibration.

Description and procedure This test is carried out by a third party exactly as described in the UNECE R100 standard. Therefore, the description is omitted here.

Deviation from standards (UNECE R100) There is no deviation from the procedure described in standard UNECE R100.

3.3.2.3.1.2. Overcharge (Pack 1)

Aim The aim of the overcharge test with active safety mechanisms is to check whether the safety mechanisms recognize that one or more cells are being overcharged and react by interrupting the charging current.

Description and procedure The pack is connected to the power supply via the high-voltage harness for the charging process. As the test is to be carried out in a thermal chamber in the laboratory, no cell is actually being overcharged to avoid the risk of thermal runaway. Instead, one of the voltage sensors that transmit the voltage of each cell to the BMS is removed from a cell and installed on a second power supply unit. This power supply unit then simulates the voltage of a cell. The voltage of the power supply unit is gradually increased during the test with the aim

that the BMS interrupts the charging current of the pack as soon as the operation limit of the charging voltage, $U_{max_degrade}$, is exceeded.

The test sequence can be seen in Figure 35. The high-level cutoff voltage is $U_{max_degrade} [V] + U_{max_degrade} [V] * 5 \%$

The time limit for all tests is limited to six hours so that the tests, including the necessary preparation and follow-up work, can be carried out within one working day. This is because tests cannot be continued overnight.

Figure 35: Process of overcharge test with safety mechanisms enabled.

Deviation from standards (UNECE R100) The overcharge test deviates from the UNECE R 100 standard in that no actual overcharging of the pack takes place (as described above, overcharging is simulated via a power supply unit). As the pack is not being overcharged, the termination criterion specified in UNECE R100 (*test is terminated if the temperature is more than 10 °C above the operating temperature*) cannot be applied here. Furthermore, for the reasons already mentioned, the upper time limit is not 12 hours, but 6 hours. In addition, no standard cycle is performed after the test in order to limit the time required for the test.

3.3.2.3.1.3. Overheat (Pack 1)

Aim The purpose of this overheat test is to examine if the safety devices recognize the too high temperature in the pack and respond by interrupting the charging or discharging current.

Description and procedure The pack is connected to the power supply via the high-voltage harness for the discharging process. As this test also has to be carried out in the laboratory, only one of the temperature sensors that transmit the temperature of each cell to the BMS is overheated instead of the entire pack in order to eliminate the risk of thermal runaway. A temperature sensor is identified in the battery pack and prepared for overheating with a blowdryer. The procedure of the test is shown in Figure 36. Since the typical maximum operation limit of NMC cells is around 55 °C, this temperature will be taken as cutoff temperature.

Figure 36: Process of overheat test with safety mechanisms enabled.

Deviation from standards (UNECE R100) The deviation of the test process from the UNECE R100 standard is that not the entire pack is overheated, but only one of the temperature sensors. For this reason, the UNECE R100 termination criterion, *the test is to be stopped when the temperature varies by less than 4 °C within 2 hours*, is disregarded.

3.3.2.3.1.4. External Short Circuit (Pack 1)

Aim The test is intended to verify whether the fuse reliably interrupts the short circuit current in the event of a short circuit.

Description and procedure This test cannot take place in the laboratory, but must be carried out on the outdoor test area for destructive tests. The positive terminal and the negative terminal of the pack are connected via a contactor, which is then being closed in order to obtain a short circuit. For the reason already mentioned, the maximum test duration is six hours. The test procedure can be taken from Figure 37.

Figure 37: Process of short circuit test with safety mechanisms enabled.

Deviation from standards (UNECE R100) The deviations from the specifications in UNECE R100 are as follows: As the test is carried out on an open area, the temperature specifications cannot be met. In addition, a standard cycle is not carried out after the test for time reasons.

3.3.2.3.1.5. Overdischarge (Pack 2)

Aim Similar to the overcharge test, the aim of the overdischarge test with active safety mechanisms is to check whether the safety mechanisms recognize the overdischarging of a cell and prevent further discharging.

Description and procedure The pack is connected to the power supply via the high-voltage harness for the discharging process. The overdischarge test is carried out in a similar way to the overcharge test: the test is carried out in the laboratory. Therefore, no cell is actually overdischarged (so as not to provoke a thermal runaway), but the overdischarging of a cell is simulated via a second power supply unit. One of the voltage sensors that communicate the voltage of each cell to the BMS is attached to this power supply unit, now acting as the cell that is being overdischarged. The test process is shown in Figure 38. According to the operation limit of the discharging voltage $U_{min_degrade}$, the low-level cutoff voltage is

$$U_{min_degrade} [V] - U_{min_degrade} [V] * 5 \%$$

For the reason already mentioned, the upper time limit for the test is six hours.

Figure 38: Process of overdischarge test with safety mechanisms enabled.

Deviation from standards (UNECE R100) The planned test procedure deviates from UNECE R100 in that no actual overdischarge of the pack is carried out, but the overdischarge of a cell via a power supply unit is merely simulated. For this reason, the two termination criteria specified in UNECE R100, *discharging is to be stopped when the temperature stabilizes with less than 4 °C variation in 2 hours* and *discharging is to be stopped when the safety mechanisms do not terminate the discharging current, but the DUT reaches 25 % of the nominal voltage*, are not considered. Furthermore, no standard cycle is performed after the test in order to limit the time required for the test.

3.3.2.3.2. Tests with Safety Mechanisms Disabled

All four of the following tests must be conducted in the outdoor test area, as the risk of a thermal runaway is very high or it is even to be deliberately triggered by the respective test.

3.3.2.3.2.1. Overcharge (Pack 1)

Aim The aim of the overcharge test with safety mechanisms disabled is to recognize how the DUT reacts in the event of an overcharge if the safety mechanisms do not interrupt the charging current. Of interest here is which parts of the pack fail and how the pack behaves in the event of a thermal runaway.

Description and procedure Figure 39 shows the courses possible in this test. The pack is connected to the power supply via the high-voltage harness for the charging process.

Figure 39: Process of overcharge test with safety mechanisms disabled.

Deviation from standards (UNECE R100) Since all tests that can cause a thermal runaway of the battery pack are not carried out in the laboratory, but on a dedicated outdoor test area, the temperature specified by UNECE R100 cannot necessarily be met, as the ambient temperature

on the test area cannot be influenced. As this test is carried out with deactivated safety mechanisms, the UNECE R100 requirement that all protection devices should be active is not met. Due to the fact that the test is carried out with deactivated safety mechanisms and with the aim of triggering a thermal runaway, the criteria of the UNECE R100 for stopping the charging phase, *overcharge protection activates* as well as *temperature exceeds max operating temperature by 10 °C*, do not apply. Furthermore, as with the other tests, the time limit is six hours instead of the twelve hours specified by UNECE R100 and the standard cycle is skipped to save time.

3.3.2.3.2.2. External Short Circuit (Pack 1)

Aim The external short circuit test with inactive safety mechanisms is intended to identify how the pack behaves (for example which component of the pack fails) in the event of a short circuit if the short circuit current cannot be interrupted by a fuse.

Description and procedure The positive terminal and the negative terminal of the pack are connected via a contactor. The short circuit is created by closing this contactor. The test process is outlined in Figure 40.

Figure 40: Process of external short circuit test with safety mechanisms disabled.

Deviation from standards (UNECE R100) As already explained, the temperature specified in UNECE R100 cannot be maintained due to the test being carried out on an open surface. In addition, the protection devices are inactive during this test and not active, as required by UNECE R100. For this reason, the criterion given by UNECE R100, *the test should be stopped when a protection system terminates the short-circuit current*, cannot be applied. As for the other tests, the standard cycle is skipped to save time.

3.3.2.3.2.3. Nail Penetration (Pack 1)

Aim The nail penetration test is performed to provoke a thermal runaway of the penetrated cell. The aim is to identify how the pack behaves during a thermal runaway of a cell and how the thermal runaway progresses.

Description and procedure Figure 41 shows the steps in this test. The pack is not being charged or discharged in the course of this test.

Figure 41: Process of nail penetration test with safety mechanisms disabled.

Deviation from standards (FreedomCAR) As this test is not included in UNECE R100, it is carried out according to FreedomCAR with no deviations.

3.3.2.3.2.4. Overheat (Pack 2)

Aim The overheat test is used to determine whether the pack's cooling system can prevent a thermal runaway. If a thermal runaway occurs despite the cooling system, the objective is to determine how the pack then behaves and how the thermal runaway spreads.

Description and procedure For this test, the cooling system integrated into the pack is put into operation. For this purpose, a cryostat is connected to the pack's cooling system via hoses. Overheating is caused by heatpads, which are positioned around a single cell in the pack and introduce heat into this cell. The battery pack is not being charged or discharged while heating the cell. The testing process is depicted in Figure 42.

Figure 42: Process of overheat test with safety mechanisms disabled.

Deviation from standards (UNECE R100) The test is carried out on an open area, which is why the temperature specifications of UNECE R100 cannot be taken into account. In contrast to the requirements of the standard, which stipulates that the protection devices should be active and the cooling system inactive, the test is carried out with inactive protection devices and an active cooling system. In addition, not the entire DUT is overheated in an oven or climatic chamber, as specified in UNECE R100, but only a single cell in the battery pack via heat pads, as described. As this test is carried out with inactive safety mechanisms and, if it cannot be prevented by the cooling system, until a thermal runaway occurs, the requirements of UNECE R100 (*gradually*

increase temperature until reaching either the operational temperature threshold for protection systems or the maximum operational temperature if no internal protection exists. Continue heating until either the DUT limits charge/discharge to prevent temperature increase or the temperature stabilizes with less than 4 °C variation within 2 hours) do not apply.

3.3.2.4. General Follow Up after Tests

Handling of Packs

As already mentioned, the packs must be deactivated in a CaCl₂-water solution for five days after the destructive tests, i.e. after the tests with deactivated safety mechanisms, so that they can then be handled and disposed of safely. Covering the tray with the pack and the CaCl₂-water solution in it with tarpaulins prevents rainwater from overflowing the tray during the deactivation period of five days. After the deactivation period, the deactivated pack is collected by the recycling company or a transport company which delivers the pack to the recycler.

Handling of Wastewater

Since the handling of the wastewater generated by the tests depends on the substances contained in the water, a sample of the wastewater must be sent to a laboratory for analysis after the packs have been deactivated. Depending on the laboratory results, a reprocessing or disposal method for the wastewater is then identified and carried out by a third party.

3.3.3. Planned Evaluation

3.3.3.1. Measuring Equipment and Parameters to be Recorded

The internal state of the battery is continuously monitored using embedded sensors that measure voltage and temperature at the cell level. These parameters are recorded via Battery Management System (BMS) communication, enabling real-time data acquisition and analysis of electrochemical behavior during the test. To complement these internal measurements, external temperature monitoring is conducted using Type K thermocouples connected to an ICPDAS data acquisition system. This system, incorporating the I-87017RW module, functions as both an analog-to-digital converter and a data logger, ensuring high-resolution thermal data collection. Additionally, direct voltage measurements are obtained independently using the ICPDAS system to validate electrical performance metrics.

To document the macroscopic effects of the abuse tests, two Sony Alpha 58 video cameras are deployed to capture high-resolution footage from multiple perspectives. This visual documentation provides valuable insight into the mechanical and structural responses of the battery under test conditions. Simultaneously, the thermal response of the system is characterized using two FLIR ResearchIR Standard 4 infrared cameras, which generate high-precision thermal imaging from different angles. These measurements facilitate the identification of localized thermal runaway initiation points and allow for the assessment of heat propagation dynamics.

Environmental conditions, which may significantly influence test outcomes, are monitored using a Eurochron EC-4406124 weather station, supplied by Conrad Electronic SE, Hirschau, Germany. This device records key meteorological parameters, including ambient temperature, humidity, wind speed and direction, precipitation, and time. Such data are essential for correlating battery performance and failure modes with external influences.

3.3.3.2. *Planned Evaluation Methods*

3.3.3.2.1. Overcharge with Safety Equipment Enabled

The Overcharge with Safety Equipment Enabled test evaluates the behavior of a complete battery pack under excessive charging conditions, with a particular focus on electrical and thermal safety mechanisms. A key aspect of the evaluation is the maximum voltage of each individual cell within the pack at the moment the charging current is interrupted. This analysis provides insights into voltage distribution, potential imbalances, and the varying responses of individual cells to overcharge conditions.

Another critical aspect is the identification of the exact moment and conditions under which the charging current is interrupted due to the activation of safety mechanisms. This evaluation allows for an assessment of the effectiveness of the built-in protection features in preventing thermal runaway or irreversible cell damage under excessive voltage conditions.

Following the overcharge phase, a 1-hour observation period is conducted, during which all available sensor data are analyzed to assess post-event stabilization, thermal propagation effects, and any residual instabilities within the battery pack. The evaluation of this time-resolved data provides a comprehensive understanding of the battery's response to overcharge stress and the effectiveness of its safety measures.

3.3.3.2.2. Overdischarge with Safety Equipment Enabled

The Overdischarge with Safety Equipment Enabled test assesses the behavior of a complete battery pack under excessive discharge conditions, focusing on electrical safety features and cell performance. A key aspect of the evaluation is the minimum voltage of each individual cell, with particular emphasis on the manipulated cell. Due to variations in test execution, only the lowest recorded voltage of the affected cell is considered, allowing for a precise assessment of critical discharge thresholds and potential safety risks.

Additionally, the discharge current behavior is analyzed to determine whether and when the system interrupts current flow upon reaching a critical undervoltage condition. This evaluation provides insight into the effectiveness of the battery's protective mechanisms in preventing deep discharge damage and ensuring system stability.

Following the discharge phase, a 1-hour observation period is conducted, during which all available sensor data are evaluated to assess post-discharge stabilization, delayed voltage recovery effects, and potential degradation of the battery pack.

3.3.3.2.3. External Short Circuit with Safety Equipment Enabled

The External Short Circuit with Safety Equipment Enabled test evaluates the battery pack's response to a sudden and uncontrolled discharge through an external circuit, focusing on electrical safety and system stability. A key aspect of the evaluation is the short-circuit current, which is analyzed to determine the peak current levels experienced under fault conditions and their impact on the electrical integrity of the pack. Additionally, the system voltage behavior is assessed to quantify the extent of voltage collapse and the recovery dynamics once the short circuit is cleared.

Another critical parameter evaluated is the duration of the short circuit event, which provides insight into the system's ability to detect and interrupt excessive current flow. The state of charge (SOC) before and after the event is calculated to determine the total energy dissipation and assess the severity of the discharge in relation to the pack's overall capacity.

Following the short circuit event, a 1-hour observation period is conducted, during which all available sensor data are analyzed to evaluate post-event stabilization, residual thermal effects, and potential degradation of the battery pack.

3.3.3.2.4. Overheat with Safety Equipment Enabled

The Overheat with Safety Equipment Enabled test assesses the battery pack's response to an external thermal stress condition, focusing on safety mechanisms and thermal propagation behavior. A key aspect of the evaluation is the temperature progression of the specific cell sensor exposed to overheating, analyzing the rate of temperature increase and determining whether critical thermal thresholds are exceeded.

In parallel, the discharge current over time is evaluated to assess the impact of increasing temperature on the battery's electrical performance. A critical point of analysis is identifying the exact moment when the discharge current is interrupted, allowing for an assessment of the activation of safety measures such as thermal protection circuits or system shutdown protocols.

Following the overheating phase, a 1-hour observation period is conducted, during which all available sensor data are analyzed to assess post-event thermal stabilization, delayed thermal effects, and potential degradation processes within the battery pack.

3.3.3.2.5. Overcharge with Safety Equipment Disabled

The Overcharge with Safety Equipment Disabled test assesses the response of a battery pack under excessive charging conditions without active protective mechanisms, focusing on electrical and thermal failure mechanisms. The evaluation includes a detailed analysis of voltage and temperature progression, as well as potential failure propagation within the pack.

The voltage and temperature evolution over time are evaluated using data from cell-integrated sensors and Type K thermocouples. The collected data allow for an analysis of critical thresholds and deviations from nominal behavior. Additionally, the charging current behavior is assessed to determine trends in charge acceptance and possible saturation effects leading to failure.

If thermal runaway (TR) does not occur, the voltage and temperature values at 12 hours after the start of charging are determined to quantify long-term thermal and electrical stability. Conversely, if thermal runaway occurs, several key parameters are derived:

- The maximum temperature at the onset of thermal runaway is calculated using BMS sensor data to define the critical failure threshold.
- The flame temperature throughout the TR event is analyzed from FLIR infrared camera recordings, providing insight into combustion intensity and thermal energy release.
- The temperature distribution within the battery housing is mapped to evaluate heat propagation and structural integrity loss.
- The progression of component destruction and failure propagation is assessed through image analysis, identifying weak points and pathways of internal damage.
- High-resolution video and thermal imaging data are systematically reviewed to reconstruct the sequence of events leading to failure.

Following the event, a 1-hour observation period is used to evaluate post-failure system behavior.

3.3.3.2.6. External Short Circuit with Safety Equipment Disabled

The External Short Circuit with Safety Equipment Disabled test evaluates the response of a complete battery pack when subjected to an uncontrolled short circuit without active safety mechanisms. A key aspect of the analysis is the short-circuit current and system voltage, which

provide insights into the severity of the fault and the electrical behavior of the system under extreme discharge conditions. Additionally, the duration of the short circuit is determined to assess how long the system can sustain such conditions before potential failure occurs.

If measurable, the state of charge before and after the event is evaluated to quantify the energy dissipation and assess the impact of the short circuit on the pack's overall capacity. The housing and cell temperatures over time are analyzed using data from BMS sensors and Type K thermocouples to characterize the thermal response of the system. Similarly, the cell voltage evolution over time is assessed via BMS data to track voltage collapse and potential recovery behavior.

In the event of thermal runaway, several additional parameters are evaluated:

- Maximum temperature at the onset of TR, derived from BMS sensor data, to identify critical thermal thresholds.
- Flame temperature progression during TR, analyzed using FLIR infrared cameras, to quantify combustion intensity and heat release.
- Temperature distribution within the housing, providing insights into internal heat propagation and potential failure points.
- Extent of component destruction and failure propagation, assessed through image analysis to track the sequential degradation of cells and structural elements.
- Video and thermal imaging data, systematically reviewed to reconstruct the sequence of events leading to catastrophic failure.

Following the event, a 1-hour observation period is conducted to evaluate post-failure system stabilization, residual thermal activity, and potential delayed degradation effects.

3.3.3.2.7. Overheat with Safety Equipment Disabled

The Overheat with Safety Equipment Disabled test evaluates the thermal response and failure behavior of a battery pack when exposed to excessive external heating without active protective measures. A key aspect of the evaluation is the temperature progression of the overheated cell, which is analyzed over time to assess the rate of temperature increase and the point at which critical thresholds are exceeded.

Additionally, the temperature distribution within the module containing the heat pads is assessed to evaluate the uniformity of heat propagation and identify potential hotspots that could lead to thermal instability. If thermal runaway occurs, several critical parameters are further analyzed:

- Maximum temperature at the onset of TR, determined from BMS sensor data, to establish the failure initiation threshold.
- Flame temperature progression during TR, captured using FLIR infrared cameras, to characterize combustion intensity and thermal energy release.
- Temperature distribution within the battery housing, providing insight into heat propagation pathways and structural degradation.
- Extent of component destruction and propagation of failure, analyzed through image data to trace the sequence of damage within the battery pack.
- High-resolution video and thermal imaging data, systematically reviewed to reconstruct the failure process and assess potential safety risks.

Following the overheating phase, a 1-hour observation period is conducted to evaluate post-event thermal stabilization, residual heating effects, and potential degradation processes within the pack.

3.3.3.2.8. Nail Penetration

The Nail Penetration test assesses the battery pack's mechanical resilience and thermal response when subjected to an internal short circuit induced by direct penetration. If thermal runaway occurs, several key parameters are evaluated to characterize the failure dynamics.

The flame temperature progression during TR is analyzed using FLIR infrared cameras, providing insight into the combustion intensity and heat release over time. Additionally, the temperature distribution within the battery housing is assessed to determine the propagation of heat and the extent of thermal stress affecting surrounding components.

The destruction and failure propagation within the battery pack are evaluated using high-resolution image analysis to identify the sequential degradation of cells and internal structures. Furthermore, video and thermal imaging data from both standard and infrared cameras are systematically reviewed to reconstruct the sequence of events leading to failure.

Following the penetration event, a 1-hour observation period is conducted to analyze post-failure stabilization, residual thermal activity, and potential delayed degradation effects.

4. Conclusion

In this deliverable, a comprehensive description of the tests performed with the developed MARBEL system was given. By utilizing the different DUTs as they were available at different stages of the project, several test setups have been created to validate the DUTs' performance and safety. In general, a testing strategy was followed that started from the very beginning, considering and making use of every testable entity in the project to steer development iterations as well as generate early measurement data, that comes in very handy when validating the final and full battery pack system and for modelling activities. The generated data and the results, as they are described in D7.2, that were gained from these experiments, will provide a comprehensive insight into the developed system, its capabilities and its safety behaviour.

5. REFERENCES

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